

**IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellbeing
In small and medium size ciTies**

D1.1. Inclusive Transformation Plan of Las Palmeras

Cordoba's Pilot

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History of changes

Page	Description
3	Update of the Executive Summary to introduce the changes in the document
8-9	Further explanations to justify the changes proposed in Cordoba's pilot and the interest to work into the patios solution
60-69	Introduction of a new section: Analysis of the impact of the changes proposed (5.4) including two tables to describe the desired impact, objectives and expected changes according to the actions proposed by the co-designed actions in the pilot, including KPIs and the indicative targets, both from the general population and the minority targeted groups in Córdoba

Executive summary

D1.1 *Inclusive Transformation Plan of Las Palmeras* describes the methodology, processes and initial results of the two-ways (top-down and bottom-up) co-design process to elaborate an Inclusive Transformation Plan to increase the Inclusive Health and Wellbeing of Las Palmeras neighbourhood, where most of the actions of the IN-HABIT project in Cordoba will be developed, as described in the WP1 of the Grant Agreement. The plan is a living document that establish the basis of the VIS to be implemented. These VIS will be adapted according to the evolution of the project.

Section 2 of the document details the stakeholder engagement and the community activation process carried out in Task 1.1 resulting in the establishment of Cordoba IN-HUB as a PPPP (public-private-people partnership) inclusive social laboratory. Sections 3 and 4, details the top-down and bottom-up co-design processes carried out by the partners UCO, AVUE, and CORDOBA (City Hall) together with the members of IN-HUB, the neighbours and other community representatives in Cordoba IN-HUB, as part of Task 1.2. Both processes have led to the co-design of the Visionary and Integrated Solutions (VIS) that will be part of this Plan.

Section 5 lists the so-called “hard” (based on infrastructure and physical solutions) and “soft” (based on social and cultural solutions) VIS that emerged as a result of the co-design process. A total of 44 VIS have been initially proposed organized in 5 areas of intervention: *Health and Wellbeing; Culture, Heritage and Art; Gender, Diversity, Inclusion, and Social Innovation; Naturalization and Environment and Infrastructure, Technology, and Digitalization*. As the project progresses the feasibility and acceptability of these VIS will be tested, and changes might be proposed. This section also includes a description of the first VIS that has been co-deployed (partially addressing Task 1.3), as well as plans for their co-deployment and co-management (partially addressing Task 1.4). The VIS description also includes KPIs for the monitoring and evaluation of the actions (partially addressing Task 1.5). The desired impact, objectives and expected changes, both from the general population and the minority targeted groups in Córdoba have been included.

Finally, Section 6 reflects on the challenges faced by the Cordoba partners in carrying out the aforementioned tasks and formulates some recommendations for the future replicability of its actions (partially addressing Task 1.6).

This ITP has been elaborated under a scenario of COVID-19 pandemic that has dramatically influenced the co-design, co-creation, co-implementation and co-management of the VIS, especially in a context as vulnerable as Las Palmeras, and has forced to unforeseen adaptations.

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List of acronyms:

Acronym	
AVUE	Asociación vecinal Unión y Esperanza de las Palmeras
CORD	Ayuntamiento de Córdoba
BOT	Book on a Tree
B4B	Bridge for Billions
DFC	Design for Change Spain
LABORELEC	Engie Laborelec
ISIMPACT	isIMPACT
ITP	Inclusive Transformation Plan
TSR	Tesserae
UCO	Universidad de Córdoba
UREAD	Universidad de Reading
VIS	Visionary and Integrated Solutions

1. Introduction

Las Palmeras Inclusive Transformation Plan (ITP) is a living document that will evolve over time according to the reality of the neighbourhood. This document presents the initial drafting co-designed with the stakeholders involved, but as the project progresses the feasibility and acceptability of the Visionary and Integrated Solutions proposed (VIS) will be tested. These VIS might be accordingly modified; new VIS might emerge, and some others might be discarded because they do not perform as expected.

IN-HABIT initial partners in Cordoba are the University of Cordoba (UCO), Cordoba’s City Hall (CORD), the Neighbourhood Association for the Union and Hope of Las Palmeras (AVUE), and as such the ones that have led the elaboration of this ITP.

The start and the implementation of IN-HABIT in Cordoba and the tasks leading to the elaboration of this ITP have been dramatically shaped by several issues, chief among them the COVID-19 pandemic. Figure 1 shows the evolution of the pandemic and the restrictions in the city. In a project based on the co-design, co-creation, co-implementation and co-management of VIS to increase health and wellbeing in a vulnerable context, the situation has had tremendous and dramatic effects. The initial proposal has had to be modified and several action lines changed. In the next sections, will be detailed both the activities effectively developed, and the measures undertaken to mitigate the difficulties faced to perform some of them.

Another issue with high influence in the Cordoba’s pilot has to do with the involvement of the City Council government. The initial proposal was negotiated with a different government team

from a different political orientation. The current government (a coalition government of 3 different political parties what makes more difficult its actions) accepted to be part of the project, but we have faced several difficulties linked to its involvement. In practice, the City Hall has experienced substantial difficulties to hire a local researcher working for IN-HABIT, as drafted in the proposal. Bureaucratic burden, lengthy procedures, public procurement barriers, language difficulties,

Figure 1: COVID-19 incidence rate and restrictions measures during IN-HABIT timeline.

etc. made that, one year after the kick-off of the project, no one was hired. These issues have created some delays in the planned activities. To address it, UCO has hired a second LCA and is developing this partner's tasks.

The previous facts have led to request an Amendment to the Grant Agreement to the EC, mainly asking 3 changes: 1) To shift the focus and the area of intervention of Cordoba's pilot from the building of a sustainable mobility corridor to create an intangible corridor connecting Las Palmeras and Axerquía neighbourhoods through the co-creation of sustainable 'patios' (inner courtyards) that will foster the naturalisation of Las Palmeras. 2) A reallocation of workload and budget between UCO and CORD. 3) The inclusion of a new partner, Patios of Axerquía (PAX), an association promoting urban regeneration strategies through social innovation processes in high patrimonial value environments, such as patios. The fact that the Amendment has not yet been approved also have delayed the deployment of some actions, but not affected to the elaboration of this ITP.

The reasons behind the shift in the intervention area are as follows. When the IN-HABIT project was initially drafted and approved (2019), the Medina Azahara Archaeological Site has just been recognised as UNESCO World Heritage Site (2018) and considered as a huge opportunity to attract tourists to Las Palmeras neighbourhood through the building of a sustainable and green mobility corridor linking the Site with the neighbourhood. The idea was greening and embellishing the area and using tourism as a trigger to break down the secular isolation of the neighbourhood from the city of Cordoba and as an attractor for development opportunities that in turn could foster inclusive health and wellbeing.

However, COVID-19 has dramatically changed the situation. According to the Town Hall records, Cordoba had one million visitors in 2019, 285.000 of them visiting the Medina Azahara site. These figures dropped down in 2020 to less than 100.000 visitors and less than 1.000 visits, respectively. The situation has slightly improved in 2021, but it is quite uncertain when previous tourist figures will be recuperated. Hence, the capacities to increase health and wellbeing in Las Palmeras neighbourhood based on tourism are really limited. Furthermore, if the corridor will not be used by a significant number of people (including tourists), there are well-founded concerns that its location at the outskirts of the city could incentivize the pillage of some elements that were planned to be introduced.

For these reasons, and to achieve the expected impacts of the IN-HABIT project in due time and to safeguard the use of taxpayer money, we propose to change the areas of intervention. We shift from building a zero-emission, green and sustainable corridor linking Las Palmeras

neighbourhood to Medina Azahara UNESCO site, to create an intangible corridor connecting Las Palmeras and Axarquía neighbourhoods through the co-creation of sustainable 'patios' (inner courtyards). We only changed the instrument to be used to boost inclusive health and wellbeing in Las Palmeras. For the rest, all the objectives and tasks of IN-HABIT remain similar, and we are pretty convinced that implementing hard VIS directly in the neighbourhood, instead of in the initial corridor might have more influence to boost IHW.

Axarquía is part of the historical city centre, and as such recognised as UNESCO World Heritage. The area is facing most of the problems of Europe's historical centres: shrinking population, ageing, gentrification, touristification, struggles to maintain the patrimonial value, abandonment of houses, lack of employment opportunities, etc. At the same time, it has one of the most active civic associations in the city. Axarquía's patios are also declared as UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage sites due to its anthropological and cultural value.

Cordoba is a medium-size city in the South of Spain, with a long historical and cultural tradition, dating back to the Roman times. It was the city capital of Al-Andalus Arab Empire (8th-13th centuries), a period characterised by wealth and splendour that left an overwhelming cultural heritage. Indeed, Cordoba is the first city holding 4 inscriptions in the World Heritage List granted by the UNESCO: [the Mosque-Cathedral \(1984\)](#); [the historical quarter surrounding it \(1994\)](#); [the Festival of the Patios \(Courtyards\) \(2012\)](#); and [Medina Azahara Archaeological site \(2018\)](#). In addition, with the rest of Spain, Cordoba shares the titles of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity awarded to [Flamenco \(2010\)](#) and [the Mediterranean Diet \(2013\)](#).

Despite this impressive historical and cultural tradition, the city experiences a high rate of unemployment, being the 2nd city of the country with the highest rate and the first capital, with a 27,8 % according to the Urban Indicators Report 2021 and includes 5 out of the 15 most marginal and lower income per habitant neighbourhoods in Spain, among them, Las Palmeras neighbourhood ([Statistics National Institute, 2021](#)), in which IN-HABIT will concentrate its innovative actions.

IN-HABIT in Cordoba focuses on undervalued resources such as culture and cultural heritage to analyse how visionary and integrated solutions (VIS) related to these resources may boost inhabitants' health and wellbeing. The project will investigate the role that patios, as sustainable and green socio-ecological systems, might have to increase people health and wellbeing and

Figure 2: Traditional patio of Cordoba. [Marco Chiesa](#).

how the co-creation and replication of patios in Las Palmeras can boost inclusive health and wellbeing in this area. The patios are one of the most representative elements of Cordoba. They exist from the Roman times and are part of the city's cultural and patrimonial value. The most traditional and famous patios in Cordoba are located in Axerquia neighbourhood, in the historical city centre and as mentioned, they are recognised as UNESCO World Heritage Site for its architecture and anthropological value.

Patios might also play a key role to address global challenges such as climate change or pandemic situations. They are green cells in the middle of the city or neighbourhoods, particularly in the historical centre where the option to build green infrastructures is quite limited because of the cultural heritage protection plans. But they are also social systems, as customarily, have been shared by several families as a common space for domestic tasks and interactions. In this respect, they can be viewed as a precedent of current co-housing trends that aim to make cities more resilient to environmental challenges and social isolation problems. The research will address the role of patios as: 1) social-ecological resilience units in the face of global challenges, such as the climatic one, or the more recent COVID-19 pandemic; 2) tangible and intangible cultural heritage sites that can boost sustainable and inclusive cities; and 3) eco-social strategies to foster inclusive health and wellbeing in Mediterranean cities, since this type of architecture can be found in most of them.

At the historical centre there are strict rules to protect the urban environment, but most of the houses have a patio, so either if houses are rebuilt or refurbished, patios still will be part of them. The richness of patios in this area might act as a valuable green infrastructure, even if in many cases they are private houses, often are shared among several families. For the case of Palmeras, 5 big patios already exist. IN-HABIT goal is to develop several VIS on them that boost their performance as social-ecological cells in the middle of the neighbourhood, as described below.

Prior to the implementation of co-design of the VIS that conformed this ITP, it was necessary to have a deep understanding of Las Palmeras. The first step was to check existing information. The second a thoughtful immersion in its reality. The intense work with neighbours and entities working in the area through interviews, meetings and workshops (that will be described in next sections) have been critical to refine this diagnosis and to engage them in the co-elaboration of

this ITP. It follows a short description of the neighbourhood, and Figure 9 displays the main outcomes. A more detailed diagnosis is presented in Appendix 4.

Las Palmeras is a small neighbourhood (less than 3000 inhabitants, according to the official data) located at the outskirts of Cordoba and characterised by segregation and disconnection (both from the city and internally among its inhabitants), high dependence on social subsidies (social housing, social canteens, subsistence aid), unstructured families and gender violence, absence of role models, failure of educational models, robberies, drug traffic, illegal activities and police raids. Health and wellbeing levels are well below the city's standards.

Wellbeing is limited by the lack of employment, the low quality of social houses, the absence of incomes to afford minimum welfare, the lack of green areas and public spaces, the low educational standards and the insecurity and even fear due to the violent behaviour of those involved in illegal activities. People do not have a feeling of belonging nor identity. Collective and community actions are almost non-existent. Disputes between families and clans are rather common and might lead to the reallocation of extended families (up to 12-15 families) in another district.

Being born in Las Palmeras is a stigma that makes many people hide their origins or the place where they live and drives them to leave the neighbourhood once they are better off. The health status is characterised by unhealthy diets and lifestyles, obesity problems, unwanted pregnancies, and drug consumption from early ages. Different inclusion strategies have been tested over the years, but they were merely short-term, top-down, and isolated initiatives that achieved very poor results and led to scepticism in terms of social transformation and better welfare and health opportunities in the neighbourhood.

Las Palmeras is organised around 5 patios though of a different nature and scale of those in Axerquia. Las Palmeras patios are dreary spaces with no green, shadowing or artistic areas. IN-HABIT visionary and integrated solutions (VIS) aim to re-naturalise and embellish Las Palmeras patios, but at the same time to promote them as spaces of social and inclusive interactions.

To overcome the challenges and barriers we propose to link Las Palmeras and Axerquia through an intangible corridor of co-created sustainable and inclusive patios that boost health and wellbeing. The intangible corridor aims to clash the existing exclusion patterns, acting as a trigger to increase IHW through culture and heritage, by integrating Las Palmeras people in the socio-economic and cultural dynamics of the city and attracting Cordoba's inhabitants to the neighbourhood.

Figure 3: Two patios of Las Palmeras. Own photo.

The outbreak of COVID-19 has reinforced all these vulnerabilities, adding new ones, such as the lack of income earning opportunities, the increase of illegal activities and the emergence of fake news and hoaxes that made coexistence even harder.

This Inclusive Transformation Plan describes the actions to increase health and wellbeing in Las Palmeras. All the VIS proposed are co-designed, co-deployed and co-managed within the public-private-people partnerships (PPPPs) that conforms Cordoba's IN-HUB, and using a gender, diversity, equity, and inclusion (GDEI) perspective.

2. IN-HUB establishment: organization, methods and achievements

Cordoba IN-HUB (IN: inclusive, HUB: nucleus of interaction) aims to be a space of interaction, working with autonomy and continuity over time; activating the human, economic and social resources of the city; creating synergies among the members and in which the protagonists are all the interested parties of the city. The establishment of the core project team and the stakeholder engagement process have started since the very beginning of the project in October 2020, and it is actively steered by the actors involved. However, the activities have had to be adapted to the pandemic situation at any period. Virtual activities have not been possible due to the lack of skills and connectivity of the neighbours.

The first steps to launch the project and create the IN-HUB have been an intense work organised at 3 levels (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Levels of work organization.

All 3 levels are necessary to create a PPPP where the co-design process can be effective and efficient thanks to the added value of all IN-HUB members: the experience of those living in the neighbourhood and knowing the demands and challenges of the context; the experience of those working in the reference context and know the area of action and the interest of other city level entities that create synergies and build a fabric for long lasting changes.

The first steps to launch the project and create the IN-HUB have been an intense work in the *neighbourhood* to get familiar with the reality and embed our potential actions in the expectations and needs of the inhabitants. Researchers have focused on building networks and create trust with Las Palmeras inhabitants.

The engagement process initiated in October 2020 and has been and continue to be an intense, continuous and constant process. Some difficulties to work with the inhabitants arose such as:

- Lack of social cohesion and mistrust among neighbours. They are not used to work together nor cooperate. The people living in each patio, and even each block might be an isolated unit.
- Low income, unemployment and uncovered basic needs: living from day to day and urgent needs make difficult to think on changes with long-term benefits.
- Socio-spatial limitations: lack of public meeting spaces and communication channels.

Figure 5: Workshops and meetings held at Las Palmeras.

- Mistrust in public administration and institutional projects.
- Lack of participation skills.
- Illegal activities that benefit from the isolation and degradation of the neighbourhood and create insecurity.

But also emerged opportunities such as the small size of the neighbourhood that facilitates the interactions and the dissemination of actions; the wishes of a better life for their kids of some families; and the willingness to participate when people perceive the direct benefits they can receive.

The second level has been to collaborate and closely work with other *institutions and NGOs* traditionally present in the area. The full involvement of the municipal social service workers of Las Palmeras civic centre and the mandate they received from the Mayor to support IN-HABIT have enormously supported these tasks. These entities have fed the project with their experience and views on the possibilities and difficulties to carry out IN-HABIT actions; helped to understand and respect the dynamics of management and power in the quarter; and facilitated the access to the neighbours and the possibility to create a horizontal participatory intervention process that led to the creation of a permanent working committee to steer this ITP, as would be described. An important step forward has been the recognition by these entities of IN-HABIT as a shared space to create synergies and work on common goals avoiding overlapping.

Some difficulties found at this level have been the past discrepancies between some entities and some reluctance to work together due to a 'sense of belonging' of neighbours, as the target groups of some entities and not of others. However, many opportunities also emerged such as the sharing of the objectives and areas of action and interest of IN-HABIT, and the facilities to work and collaborate online when the pandemic restrictions hampered other means.

Finally, an intense work has been developed at the city level, to spread and disseminate the project, informing to different collectives, associations and institutions about its objectives and activities and searching for synergies and complementarities with other projects currently running in the city, aiming to ground the project actions in the life of the city and to boost its sustainability and legacy beyond the project lifetime. Additionally, the involvement of Cordoba's

civil society in our actions and IN-HUB, might minimise some of the difficulties found at the government level.

The IN-HUB is conceived as an open space that might evolve according with the dynamics of the project. Its creation, consolidation and expansion is fully embedded in the process of co-design, co-creation, co-deployment and co-monitoring of this ITP.

Figure 6: Steps for the IN-HUB establishment.

All these tasks have been developed in a pandemic scenario that was even harder in Las Palmeras. Mobility and gathering restrictions caused delays and cancellation of planned activities, fear of contagion prevented participation, misunderstanding and fake news created hoaxes and incertitude, poor socioeconomic status and low educational level made more difficult protection measures. Cordoba team profited any window of opportunity to do activities and continue the dynamization process, but often was not possible.

2.1. Establishment of core project team & stakeholder mapping

The UCO team is composed of a project coordinator (PC) in charge of the management and coordination of the whole project, a scientific coordinator (SCo) entitled to oversee the theoretical and methodological aspects of the project, two local community activators (LCA) with proven expertise in social inclusion of vulnerable groups and performing fieldwork tasks (diagnostic of the situation, stakeholder engagement, IN-HUB establishment, primary and secondary data collection and reporting, gendered landscape), one key local contact (KLC) for communication and dissemination purposes, and a project manager (PM) to tackle and monitor the managerial issues of the project. Additionally, other researchers with proven expertise in naturalization, social innovations, infrastructures and health and wellbeing are supporting specific tasks.

This team has worked hand by hand with AVUE representatives and with the social service workers nominated by the City Hall. Furthermore, AVUE has recently hired 3 young women from

the neighbourhood that are acting as local observers and LCAs. Their knowledge of the area and their acceptance by the inhabitants help to overcome some barriers. At the same time, they are acquiring professional and empowerment skills.

Stakeholder engagement and governance of project activities is foreseen at three levels:

1. Cordoba IN-HUB, with representatives of the 4 helixes: civil society; public administration; business; research and education.
2. Las Palmeras neighbourhood, with a permanent committee of local inhabitants working in the project.
3. Policy level, with a technical committee of representatives from the City Council in the main thematic areas: social services, sustainable urbanism, health, culture and heritage, digital infrastructure and smart city, etc.

The representatives of the institutions/organisations leading the project (UCO, CORD and AVUE) oversee these three levels of participation and governance.

To involve different stakeholders representing the local community of intervention, but also the public and private sectors interested in inclusive health and wellbeing through culture and cultural heritage, a first mapping exercise was realised following the 4 helixes stakeholder engagement approach. The strategy for identifying stakeholders followed the principles of completeness and inclusiveness, so all the potentially relevant components of Las Palmeras community, and of the city were included.

At the neighbourhood level, there was a first contact with ‘key informants’ of local/internal associations such as NGOs, social services, religious brotherhoods, the parish community, the sports centre, the local radio with which AVUE traditionally collaborates. ‘Key informants’ helped LCAs to get access to the neighbourhood and mediated the communication with different target groups. Additionally, different external associations and organizations working in the neighbourhood were informed about IN-HABIT and invited to participate. Other city and regional level actors and institutions were identified and asked to contribute.

During the training of LCAs in stakeholders’ engagement and gender issues developed as part of WP5 (*Citizen engagement, inclusive business models and PPPs to boost IHW*) tasks, a second mapping exercise was performed to refine the first one. Identified actors and representatives were placed in a graph according with the four helix dimensions (see Graph 1, Appendix 5).

2.2. Open call and communication campaign to select the members of the local IN-HUB

According to the IN-HABIT Glossary, the IN-HUB is a laboratory of social innovation where people coming from different public and private organisations or as individuals work together for social change. It is a networking strategy for the enhancement of cooperation aimed at the co-design and co-management of spaces and a platform for structural dialogue and collaboration. The IN-HUB is both a physical place for meeting and sharing and an organisational structure to facilitate the transformative process in the cities.

The Cordoba IN-HUB aims to steer the local Private Public People Partnership (PPPP) to deliver visionary and integrated solutions (VIS) through the mobilisation of culture and heritage to improve health and wellbeing in Las Palmeras and the city of Cordoba. The identified stakeholders from Las Palmeras neighbourhood and the city of Cordoba were contacted and invited to be part of the Cordoba IN-HUB.

Figure 7: Patios de la Ciencia (Science courtyards)

The communication campaign of the official IN-HUB launch in Cordoba started on January 2021 through the mentioned process of key stakeholders' identification and contact establishment, regular mass-media communication of the project, and other communication and dissemination events such as *Patios de la Ciencia* (Science courtyards) during the 2021 European Researchers' Night (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, 25th of September 2021).

The IN-HABIT launch of the international communication campaign took place the 27th of September 2021, with an invited guest, the cultural promotor Fernando Vacas, and various media news, radio programmes about IN-HABIT and its actions on Onda Las Palmeras, etc.

The official establishment of the Cordoba IN-HUB took place on the 3rd of November 2021 in a two-session event, one in the morning in the Rectorate of the University of Cordoba, and the other one in the afternoon in Las Palmeras main square. Both events have been the result of months of working on key stakeholders' identification and contact establishment, and recurrent meetings to communicate the project and its objectives at both, city and neighbourhood levels, following a people-public-private-partnership (PPPP) approach.

At the morning meeting, 51 participants from 35 different entities attended and a Manifesto of Adhesion (see Appendix 6) was signed by most of them. Five thematic action areas and working groups were established, and participants invited to decide to which of them they aim to contribute:

1. **Health and Wellbeing;**
2. **Culture, Heritage and Art;**
3. **Gender, Diversity, Inclusion, and Social Innovation;**
4. **Naturalization and Environment;**
5. **Infrastructure, Technology, and Digitalization.**

Participants were also invited to express their level of engagement in IN-HUB activities at the time of signing the Manifesto, but they also can change their decisions over time:

1. **continuous** (participation in the sub-thematic groups and in the co-design, co-deployment, and co-management of the actions, search for synergies with other actions, etc.);
2. **occasional** (participate in specific activities, assess actions in their area of expertise, etc.);
3. **information** channel (knowing the actions, information exchange, etc.).

The second part of the official launch of the IN-HUB took place in the afternoon in the main square of Las Palmeras. It was an event co-designed with the neighbours, as will be described in section 1.4. It is worth to mention that all neighbours were invited to attend from October 2021 onwards, through door-to-door notification of the launch event. The project was explained to each family and a project leaflet was handed in to a total of 700 families.

In this event actively participated a pilot group of 15 neighbours even if others were around but not fully involved. Additionally, other members of the IN-HUB joined the event. And AVUE and the representatives of the City Hall had a leading role. Participants were invited to

Figure 8: IN-HABIT Project meetings at UCO and Las Palmeras.

contribute with ideas and proposals on different aspects related to health and wellbeing, and various experts guided the working groups. A first proposal of co-designed VIS was elaborated, and the five initial thematic groups were reduced to three:

1. **Healthy lifestyles**

2. **Art, culture and infrastructure**
3. **Naturalization and environment**

Some experts in each of these areas were invited to participate and interact with the neighbours.

Consent forms were signed for participation in all activities of the IN-HUB and for the right to use images/videos on the project's social media and channels.

2.3. Assignment of specific roles (local community activators/representatives, UAB, thematic sub-groups) and their activities

The two LCAs were selected based on an open call and hired by UCO to support fieldwork activities in Cordoba. They have made a deep immersion in the reality of the neighbourhood, identifying the key actors and the main problems and creating networks and synergies with other actors. They support stakeholder engagement at the local level, by identifying community leaders, networks and organisations working for social change. They reach out people living in the neighbourhood, with specific attention to the most vulnerable ones, in order to engage them in the co-design process of Las Palmeras VIS. They have been involved in desk and field research activities such as the secondary data collection through networking with local private and public entities, translation of materials, and report writing. They have also been responsible of primary data collection through interviews, questionnaires, running workshops and focus groups and writing down reports.

LCAs have been trained by TSR, UREAD, ISIM, BOT and DFC partners (as part of WP5), to use tools to motivate the neighbours, to become active change-makers and to drive actions, to perform digital communication tasks, and to undertake gender-based research and impact assessment activities. Accordingly, they have started to organize and facilitate events for citizen engagement, VIS co-design and research tasks in the field. LCAs are fully involved in the following activities:

1. Co-design and field research task under the scientific coordination and guidance of project partners: collecting and analysing data and, summarizing results (i.e. reports); co-design and run workshops and research/assessment actions.
2. Communication and stakeholder and community engagement strategies: keeping relations with stakeholders and IN-HABIT partners; supporting IN-HABIT communication

strategy at local level; explaining and communicating the project, the research objectives and intended results to target groups; helping managing conflicts and ethical issues/obstacles concerned with the participation of minorities; translating data into usable information in order to create an engaging, informative, compelling story.

After analysing the different potential actions to be developed in Las Palmeras proposed at the IN-HUB launching, a first meeting of the thematic groups was held on the 3rd of December 2021 to co-design VIS (see section 5).

In this meeting, the need to create a User Advisory Board was described and a call for the representatives of each thematic group with a GDEI perspective opened. The final members selected are representatives of the following institutions:

1. Health and Wellbeing group: Don Bosco Foundation.
2. Culture, Heritage and Art: ARTDECOR and Club UNESCO Cordoba.
3. Gender, Diversity, Inclusion, and Social Innovation: Women Institute at Cordoba.
4. Naturalization and Environment: Botanical Garden.
5. Infrastructure, Technology, and Digitalization: Corduba Tech Association.
6. One woman from the core pilot group of Las Palmeras.
7. One young woman of Las Palmeras.

Finally, after the co-deployment of the first VIS in the central square and the joint actions to organise the Christmas party, a committee, *Las Palmeras Committee*, was created to supervise and boost this ITP. The different entities working in the neighbourhood and several neighbours decided to join forces with INHABIT creating this permanent committee that is meeting every fortnight to plan and prioritize proposals, to monitor and to evaluate the VIS already underway or concluded. The continuous feedback will allow improvement on the development of the ITP. The Committee is a fundamental co-deployment and co-management tool insofar as it allows efficient community planning and continuous monitoring, relying on the experiences and knowledge of the neighbourhood.

Various action areas have been established within the IN-HUB for coordination, communication, co-design, implementation, impact assessment, and gendered landscape purposes; key roles, partners and stakeholders have been identified and decision-making mechanisms have been established for each action area. These tasks are developed by the Cordoba team (UCO, AVUE, Cordoba City Council), with the support of transversal project partners with expertise in stakeholder engagement, assessment, GDEI perspective, mindset change, and communication

and dissemination activities (TSR, ISIM, UREAD, BOT), and local administration/departments in the areas of interest (health and wellbeing, culture and heritage, gender and diversity).

In the communication area, a Key local contact (KLC) from the UCO team was appointed as communication and social media manager in collaboration with BOT. In the co-design area, the key roles are those of the LCAs and facilitators such as DFC. In the co-deployment area, the key roles are fulfilled by LCAs, local observers/community representatives and Las Palmeras committee.

Other partners involved in this action area are the transversal project partners involved in the implementation of VIS on the field (ISIM, TSR, UREAD, BOT, LABORELEC), the related local administration/departments and, private contractors and providers. Finally, in the impact assessment area, the key roles are assigned to the SCo, LCAs, local observers/community representatives, and the transversal project partner coordinating this task (ISIM).

2.4. Setting up principles, procedures, and processes of collaborative development and participation

The Córdoba IN-HUB Manifest of Adhesion set up the principles, procedures, and process of collaborative participation inside of the IN-HUB, and the different levels of commitment or participation (regular, occasional, or information channel). The Manifest informs stakeholders on the IN-HABIT project and its objectives, that is to boost the inclusive access to health and wellbeing in small and medium size cities by exploring the effect of visionary and integrated solutions based on undervalued resources such as culture and heritage (Córdoba), food (Riga), human-animal bonds (Lucca), and arts and environment (Nitra) from a gender, diversity, equity and inclusion perspective. These innovations are going to be implemented in marginalised areas and targeting mainly vulnerable groups, and are going to be co-designed, co-deployed and co-managed by and for local inhabitants.

For this purpose, the Cordoba IN-HUB is created as a laboratory of social action and innovation. The IN-HUB is going to function based on people-public-private partnership (PPPP) schemes, by integrating local inhabitants, associations, NGOs, public institutions, private enterprises and actors in all its actions and by creating synergies with other projects taking place in the city.

The Manifest aims to be a compromise of participation in the Cordoba IN-HUB and thus a living document that will be adapted continuously to the IN-HUB dynamic and needs of its members.

The roles, levels of participation, ways of functioning and decision-making have been established through a participative process. The IN-HUB Córdoba is organised around the five action areas, whose members are going to meet at least once by trimester to co-design different innovative solutions and co-deploy and co-manage them.

Annual meetings will be organised with all members of the Cordoba IN-HUB to share project advances and establish new lines of action. The UAB will also meet at least once at trimester. Finally, Las Palmeras Committee will meet every 2 weeks to boost the co-deployment of VIS and co-monitor them.

The stakeholders who signed the Cordoba IN-HUB Manifest agreed with the objectives and functioning principles of the IN-HUB and expressed their wish to contribute to the fulfilment of the established commitments from their field of action, and to participate in the development of the innovative solutions that will be launched in the intervention areas (see Appendix 6).

3. Co-design of visionary and integrated solutions (VIS): top-down driven process

Prior to the implementation of the VIS co-design process, an in-depth analysis of the neighbourhood situation and a process of embedding in its reality have been undertaken. Researchers have put into place a process of dynamization to inform about the project, engage neighbours, and make them accept to participate in IN-HABIT actions, as previous steps to co-design, co-deploy and co-monitor this ITP.

Figure 9 display the main results of the analysis that are described in Appendix 2.

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHICS

- Male 1126
- Female 1086
- 0-17 years old 598
- 18-65 years old 1401
- > 66 years old 196

HOUSING AND INFRASTRUCTURE

- 700 (social) flats (70-125 m²)
- 5 patios (squares)
- 1 ~ 7 people per-home
- Low quality housing
- Electricity, water and sewage deficiencies
- Illegal cannabis production

SOCIO-ECONOMICS

- Unemployment rate: > 70 % (lack of data)
- Average income/person: < 6.810€ (6th quarter with the lowest income in Spain)
- Informal economy and illegal activities

EDUCATION AND TRAINING

- High rate of school absenteeism
- High rate of school drop-out
- Families prefer schooling children outside the neighbourhood
- No secondary nor vocational training facilities
- Lack of social and educational skills
- Lack of digital competences

ASSOCIATIVE NETWORK

- Associations working on Las Palmeras:
- Associations from Las Palmeras:

PUBLIC SPACES AND ENVIRONMENT

- Dirty and degraded public spaces
- No green areas nor leisure spaces
- Lack of light areas and streetlights (by night)
- Insecure space (violence, cohabitation patterns)

IDENTITY, STIGMA AND VULNERABILITY

- Discrimination and stigma
- Low self-esteem
- Institutional mistrust
- Loneliness and isolation
- Gender-based violence and discrimination
- Violence
- Conflicts between familiar clans
- Insecurity (especially at night)

MENTAL HEALTH AND HEALTHY HABITS

- Lack of sport facilities
- Unhealthy diets
- Unwanted pregnancies
- Stress to cover basic needs
- Drug addictions
- Sleep problems / lack of sleep (noise, bad habits)
- Low self-care and lack of hygiene

COMUNICATION AND CONNECTIVITY

- Limited services (1 bus stop, no taxis, no delivery)
- Outskirt location (separated of the city by a by-pass road)
- Limited connection with city centre

COVID-19

- No incomes at lockdown (increase of illegal activities)
- Loss of employment (informal work)
- Limited access to basic needs and medicines
- Health inequality
- Extended family units living in limited spaces
- Increase in social conflicts but decrease in criminality (more patrolling)
- Misinformation and hoaxes
- Loneliness
- Excuse for school absenteeism

Figure 9: Diagnosis of Las Palmeras.

Based on this context, and to offer an adequate response to the needs of the neighbourhood and its neighbours, different workshops and methodologies have been designed and applied in collaboration with other project members, to build a cyclical process (Figure 10) with continuous feedback of the six different phases as a barebone element of the top-down and bottom-up processes.

Activating the human and social capital existing in the community (neighbours, entities that work in the neighbourhood, public or private entities of interest for and in the project) boost the process of engagement, while the continuous participation fosters change in the context (attracting new actors) and in the actors (becoming empowered). This whole cyclical process aims to trigger changes in values to motivate action and participation. Previously, it has been necessary to build a relationship of trust over time that allows joint work, nurtures the social capital, empowers people and generates transformations. Transformation is based on the co-design of a range of innovative solutions, for which understanding the context and defining the community of intervention have been essential.

Along with that understanding and defining the community, it has also been necessary to define a theoretical framework of joint participation with different actors involved in the neighbourhood and the city, to create a PPPP dynamic of joint work, to co-define some common goals and to collect knowledge and expertise from the people and entities working in the context.

A key element of this knowledge has been the knowledge of the social memory of the community (previous experiences with project, city institutions, internal dynamics of collaboration and conflicts between neighbours, entities of the neighbourhood...)

as a conditioning factor for working tools, boosting participation processes, or understanding the need for change, and the social behaviour of Las Palmeras.

Figure 10: Cyclical process of engagement.

Figure 11: Steps for co-design process.

All these processes and steps have been followed prior to the implementation of the top-down process that made possible to obtain a social and conceptual image of the neighbourhood, the entities that make it up and the interrelationships that exist, thus facilitating the work of the rest of the IN-HABIT project members, as exposed in the following sections.

3.1. Working methods and management of the Toolkit

The [GDEI Toolkit](#) provides a set of guidelines, methods, and tools for the wider engagement of stakeholders in the people-public-private partnerships (PPPPs). It includes instructions for stakeholders mapping and local needs assessment, selection criteria, incentive mechanisms, structure, working rules and diversity management procedures, co-design methodology, and the necessary guidelines and templates for the creation and management of the local IN-HUB.

The GDEI Toolkit was also the basis for the training of LCAs to support the inclusive process of co-creation, co-design, co-management, and co-monitoring of VIS, with specific attention at the engagement of less represented and more at risk of exclusion stakeholders.

The GDEI Toolkit includes guidelines, methods and tools such as:

- The Glossary, which provides a common definition for all the partners of the main terms adopted by the project.
- The Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (GDEI) guidelines, which supports the wider, just and equal participation of all social groups in project activities.
- The IN-HUB Management Handbook, which includes guidelines and templates for setting the local PPPPs coordination structure, co-monitoring procedures, tools and guidelines for VIS co-design.

3.2. Training of LCAs in working methods

Between March and April 2021, a 5 days training programme in project methods was organized and delivered to LCAs selected in the four IN-HABIT cities. Local activators were trained by transversal partners (TSR, UREAD, DFC, ISIM, BOT) in co-design, citizen engagement, GDEI, mindset change, communication, and impact assessment methodologies and tools.

These sessions -and the support in the following months- led to a feedback process being a valuable opportunity to share the experience of the fieldwork carried out in each city with the expertise of the transversal PP and to create bonds among all the LCAs involved in the project.

The LCA training included the following topics:

- Understanding the transformation process aimed by IN-HABIT: Get together; Frame 4 change; Urban reconnaissance and IHW impact evaluation methods and tools.
- Gender, diversity, equity, and inclusion (GDEI) approach; Setting the I in IHW; GDEI approach; Inclusive evaluation in practice, incentives, and ethical considerations; Stakeholder mapping.
- Communication and storytelling: capturing inputs for communication; local communication plans and tools; storytelling for inclusion; impact assessment through storytelling.
- From vision to co-design: assessing the co-suffix; thread mapping; co-creating; I Can Mindset.
- Managing the IN-HUB: purpose and management; GDEI Stakeholder Engagement Toolkit; local action planning.

As part of this training process, some transversal partners (TSR, UREAD and BOT) have been invited to carry out a specific field visit to the city. In this visit, it is also intended to work jointly with the IN-HUB members and with the neighbours to obtain more specific results adapted to the context of each space. Unfortunately, the COVID-19 situation forced to postpone this visit in Cordoba that is planned for the next months.

3.3. Co-design of IHW indicators

A two-way (top-down and bottom-up) co-design process of inclusive health and wellbeing (IHW) indicators was employed to embed both researchers' and stakeholders' knowledge, needs,

and perspectives into the transformation of the target public spaces in Cordoba - Las Palmeras patios and central square, with a GDEI perspective.

The top-down co-design process included a first proposal of IHW indicators proposed by ISIM partner and based on the review of relevant assessment frameworks and metrics on health and wellbeing at European and international levels (e.g., [OECD – Better life initiative – Compendium of OECD wellbeing indicators 2011](#); [EUROSTAT -Final report of the expert group on quality of life indicators 2017 edition](#); [UNDP-SDGs assessment indicators](#); [WHO-QOL metrics on mental health](#); [International Labour Organization indicators on labour inclusion](#); [EKLIPSE indicators on NBS assessment](#)). The first set of IHW indicators was selected and shared with Cordoba city partners for further feedback on validity, measurability, and specificity in respect to the city context.

The bottom-up process involved local inhabitants in the co-design of IHW indicators and integrated the most significant expected changes regarding health and wellbeing from the inhabitants' perspective. The bottom-up participative process used a co-design methodology to identify specific indicators related to the needs and perspective of people at risk of discrimination and exclusion such as women, youth, elderly, families (with small children), ethnic and religious minorities, LGBTQI+ people, and people with disabilities.

The bottom-up co-design consisted of the identification of city-specific indicators through semi-structured interviews with stakeholders and inhabitants at the local level. Twenty-six face-to-face semi-structured interviews with local stakeholders and inhabitants were carried out in Las Palmeras between the 18th and 31st of April 2021. The respondents were selected to assure diversity by age, disability, ethnic origin, gender identity, and sexual orientation. Some respondents were representatives of local social service agencies, public schools, the City Council, civic associations and NGOs, private companies, religious institutions or associations, and students. Seventeen respondents lived in Las Palmeras, from which 9 have worked actively in social projects in the neighbourhood for more than 5 years.

Participants were guided by means of the following discussion points:

- Identification of the most relevant aspects of health and wellbeing.
- Identification of the most significant changes that vis could produce on local people's health and wellbeing (in general and for specific groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion).
- Effects of the covid-19 pandemic on inhabitants' health and wellbeing.

The final list of IHW indicators (see Appendix 7) for the pilot of Cordoba is thus the result of literature review, consultation of local project partners, local inhabitants and, institutional representatives of target groups during the co-design phase. Cordoba's IHW indicators were complemented with common indicators for the four cities on mental health, socio-demographic and GDEI characteristics and COVID-19 effects on healthy lifestyles (see [D7.1 - Inclusive Impact Assessment Plan](#), for further details).

3.4. Secondary data collection

The secondary data collection at city level represents an essential supportive activity for the following tasks of the IN-HABIT project:

- The evaluation of the impact of the project on health and wellbeing of local inhabitants, particularly on those groups at risk of exclusion and discrimination, which is part of WP7.
- The analysis of gendered landscapes, which includes the mapping of spatial inequalities by gender and elicitation of gender, diversity, equity, and inclusion (GDEI) approaches to local decision making, urban regeneration, and innovations, which is part of WP6.
- The elicitation of healthier behaviours among inhabitants, especially vulnerable groups, which is part of WP6.

Besides the primary data (collected through the survey designed by IN-HABIT and administered to the relevant target groups), secondary data, available from existing surveys and other administrative sources, at an appropriate geographical level have contributed to the fulfilment of the above-mentioned tasks. The use of these two types of data is complementary to address two main methodological issues:

- Establish an appropriate and representative sampling framework for the collection of primary data through INHABIT surveys.
- Establish an appropriate evaluation framework.

Parallel to this work, secondary data for a series of indicators that cover relevant aspects related to health and wellbeing at the municipal level were analysed. The data were collected at the:

- Geographical level: city level (Cordoba) and neighbourhood level (Las Palmeras).
- Gender, diversity, equity, and inclusion (GDEI) level, by providing data for various groups identified according to their gender, ethnicity, age, disability, religion or belief etc.

All indicators were disaggregated, if data sources were available, by the relevant IN-HABIT characteristics including: sex or gender; ethnicity (or nation of birth); age; disability; sexual orientation; religion or belief. When possible, indicators captured the intersectionality between more than one characteristic: gender and age, gender and ethnicity, etc. In addition, all the relevant data sources (research reports and tables of anonymized data) were included in the secondary data collection and shared with the involved project partners through the IN-HABIT Data Repository.

3.5. GDEI determinants of spatial and functional elements/or Gendered landscape

To construct gendered landscapes is part of the tasks included in WP6 (*Enabling behavioural changes with a gender and diversity perspective*). Gender landscapes aim to question the design of the urban space and its effects through men and women's different experiences and to improve inclusivity across three pillars:

- Institutions: mainstreaming gender and diversity in administrative processes.
- Lived experiences: understanding the extent to which the cities are lived differently by different social groups, and how to design an inclusive urban space for all.
- Health and wellbeing inequality: mapping the extent of inequality in health and wellbeing in the cities to understand how urban design affects these aspects.

Each pillar includes various actions or aspects that have been or are still to be investigated at the municipal level.

Pillar 1. Institutions

- Accountability: the ability for anyone to check on the public action and trigger judiciary consequences is essential. Is there a GDEI audit? Is there a GDEI impact assessment?
- Knowledge-based: to deal with GDEI issues appropriately, public policies need to be based on scientifically sound objective evidence. Are there initiatives based on a gender analysis?
- Stakeholder involvement: a decision process cannot be inclusive without a fair representation of all parts. It is also necessary to provide a transparent mapping of all stakeholders.

Pillar 2. Lived experience

- Sampling: survey respondents across the city on the key dimensions of their daily life, such as work, education, caring, transport, leisure...
- Estimation: estimate the influence of the main determinants of individuals' behaviours and choices, including urban design and existing gender power structures.
- Perspective taking simulate what would be the behaviours and choices of a group (e.g. women) under different circumstances (e.g. using bus instead of car).
- Mapping: represent the alternative scenarios in the current urban space to highlight its limitations.
- Recommendations: produce tailored recommendations.

Pillar 3. Health and wellbeing inequality

- Sampling: surveying respondents across the cities and record their locations. It allows us to associate a measure of health and wellbeing at specific locations.
- Kriging: estimating health and wellbeing in non-sampled places which produces a heat map of health and wellbeing for the whole cities.
- Contours: locating precisely hot and cold spots of health and wellbeing using contour lines.
- Inequality: reproducing the previous steps for another group (e.g. women). Then, identify locations where women have lower health and wellbeing.
- Recommendations: produce tailored recommendations.

The results of Cordoba gender landscape will be presented in deliverable D6.2 (to be delivered by June 2022). It follows a description of the tasks developed so far, and how they have fed this ITP.

The first objective, reflected in the Pillar 1, has been to produce a comprehensive mapping of the institutional frameworks that support decision-making at the city level in order to understand the extent to which gender and diversity aspects have been taken into account in the formulation of policies at different levels, from political commitment to the possible implementation of action plans. This is an important aspect of the city's gender and diversity landscape.

It has been necessary to conduct background research and to obtain information directly from the City's political and administrative offices, with the support of the neighbourhood equality promoter. In this sense, it has been quite a complex task due to the limited open information

existing in administration reports and because the lack of detailed and homogenized data by gender at the neighbourhood or city level. Furthermore, information, when available, has not been easy to access or is out of date.

Although a declaration of political intention exists, including different political lines of action, which are synthesized in the Gender Transversal Plan of the City of Córdoba, the specific actions fully developed to comply with these lines are limited and often disconnected. This Plan was conceived as a strategic framework with a medium and long-term view to apply a full gender equality vision to all the municipal policies to reach a real equality city.

The main axes are social co-responsibility, empowerment, and gender mainstreaming, as well as the objectives that are reorganization and improvement of public management related to gender equality, city free of gender violence, inclusive city in equality and caring city. Unfortunately, even if these lines of work are proposed, there is still a long way to fully include these policies in concrete lines of actions that translate into a real change in gender equality.

In 2021, only one out of four women holds a position of responsibility in the [City Council](#) or the [Provincial Council](#). Out of the 56 senior positions elected by the political parties in both institutions, less than half are held by women (2021). The statistics include the management bodies of the City Council of the capital and the Provincial Council. Identifying the policies that can have undesired and unexpected discriminatory effects is essential when proposing a transformation with an inclusive perspective. IN-HABIT will concentrate efforts in highlighting and addressing these issues.

3.6. Baseline Study on IHW: survey, storytelling, focus groups and interviews

IN-HABIT assessment framework developed in WP7 (*Assessing the impact of visionary and integrated solutions on Inclusive Health and Wellbeing*) includes both quantitative and qualitative research tools to monitor the inclusive health and wellbeing in the four cities because of the implemented innovations during the lifetime of the project (ex-ante y ex-post).

For the ex-ante assessment of the state of health and wellbeing of Córdoba's inhabitants (Task 7.3, WP7), a baseline study was undertaken in Las Palmeras as the intervention area, and the Córdoba city, as a control area. The following quantitative and qualitative tools were used:

- One survey to test the adequacy of the selected health and wellbeing indicators.
- Context analysis from secondary data collected at the city and neighbourhood levels.
- One focus group with 6 participants.
- 5 storytelling on relevant health and wellbeing dimensions.
- No semi-structured interview was needed in Cordoba's case.

3.6.1. *Determinants of IHW according to interviews, storytelling and focus group*

The bottom-up process involved local inhabitants in the co-design of IHW indicators and integrated the most significant expected changes regarding health and wellbeing from the inhabitants' perspective. The interviews have permitted to know better the reality and complexity of the neighbourhood and the relationships among the neighbours, and the co-design of city specific indicators on socio-economic wellbeing and healthy lifestyle based on their experiences.

For the inhabitants of Las Palmeras, wellbeing and health are understood in a global, integral, and comprehensive perspective: people should be physically, psychologically, spiritually satisfied, from emotional, economic, family, environmental and community points of view: "feel well with my surroundings, with nature".

In this sense, IHW includes many aspects such as: safety; relational network; physical health and healthy lifestyles (e.g., good nutrition, hygiene, sufficient sleep as it may affect mood or school attendance); healthy leisure alternatives and appropriated spaces (need of and claim for public and common spaces) or healthy environment. The basis to promote health and wellbeing is to guarantee the basic needs of individuals and families (economic, cultural, educational) with stable sources of income (avoiding thus stress and insecurity). But wellbeing and health also depends of the quality of coexistence with others, not having anxiety, leave in peace with oneself and the environment, and mental openness towards what is different (e.g., not living in a stigmatized and self-stigmatized ghetto).

Participants in the interviews perceived the following aspects of health and wellbeing as the most relevant ones:

- Having the basics needs covered (a stable source of income, a job, a roof, food). This aspect was highlighted as closely related to psychological wellbeing (the level of stress), as well as with dignity and social relationships.

- Feeling a sense of security, both at home and in the neighbourhood. The safety dimension was also mentioned in relation to psychological wellbeing (feeling calm, living with tranquillity).
- Quality of public environment (quiet, well maintained, pleasant and safe for all age groups) that was connected to personal satisfaction (feeling well about what surrounds me) and health. In particular, the lack of a quiet environment negatively affected inhabitants' sleep, good mood and school attendance.
- Quality of housing, which implied living in an adequate space (several generations might share small rooms with clear negative consequences for personal development), but also having good habits like house cleaning and care.
- Healthy habits like regular contact with nature, regular physical activity, sleep well, adequate personal care and hygiene, access to healthy food.
- Social/relational and psychological wellbeing such as self-stigmatization and equity, personal growth, academic/career success, feeling valued/loved, being motivated and have targets, having access to equal opportunities (wealth, education, employment).

Figure 12 displays the IHW dimensions for Las Palmeras people, based on their main contributions in the primary data collection.

Figure 12: IHW Dimensions and sub-indicators.

3.6.2. IHW baseline according to the survey

The survey to establish IHW baseline was run online between September and November 2021. Table 1 shows the number of participants in the intervention and control areas by target groups.

Target group	Palmeras	Control Group	Other	Total
Women	165	102	5	272
Disabilities	18	17	1	36
Young (18/30)	97	57	4	158
Elderly	21	15	0	36
Minorities	36	6	0	42
LGTBIQ+	15	16	1	32
TOTAL	262	184	10	456

Table 1: Participants by group.

The results have been divided according to the delimited indicators in the different dimensions and in their corresponding subdimensions, while showing the differentiated results of the inhabitants of the neighbourhood and those of the rest of the city's inhabitants.

The data shows that there are indicators with similar results, whose variation is less than 5% (e.g., psychological wellbeing or satisfaction relationship with people living in their neighbourhood) while there are others, where there is big variations with a difference of more than 30% (e.g., the ease of finding a place to play sports or the inability to cover basic needs). A detailed analysis of these results, will be presented in D7.3 (Baseline study on IHW report) but some relevant outcomes are:

- Sense of discrimination based on the place of origin as well as a lesser sense of security in public spaces.
- The neighbours (target group) experience a higher level of civil and social engagement and some change making attitude.
- The neighbourhood needs more public infrastructure related to green area as well as more attention from the institutions to increase and improve the negative vision of the neighbourhood.
- No leisure opportunities nor leisure infrastructure, hence no healthy options for free time.
- High rate of unemployment and more job insecurity than in other city areas.

Figure 13 display different aspects of the survey and its results, segregating the data obtained from the different groups and their connection with the IHW dimensions and subdimensions.

Intervention Group — People living or frequenting Las Palmeras neighbourhood

Control Group — The rest of the inhabitants of Cordoba

> SOCIAL WELL-BEING

> EQUALITY AND DISCRIMINATION

> PERCEPTION OF SECURITY

> SOCIAL INCLUSION

> SOCIAL COHESION

Participants from the intervention group show a **good level of social cohesion** and collective self esteem, trust in others, solidarity among inhabitants and social network support within and among families.

> SPATIAL WELL-BEING

> ACCESSIBILITY OF RESOURCES IN THE NEIGHBOURHOOD

> SATISFACTION WITH THE NEIGHBOURHOOD AND URBAN GREEN AREAS

Participants from the intervention group **report a lower satisfaction for public green areas**, moreover, they believe that the image of their neighbourhood is negative and has worsened in the past years due to the **abandonment from the institutions**.

> PHYSICAL HEALTH AND HEALTHY LIFESTYLES

> HEALTHY HABITS

> LEISURE AND FREE TIME

People from the intervention group are satisfied with the way they spend their free time. However, they express **dissatisfaction with the quality of the time spent** in the local public spaces and **lack of healthy leisure opportunities**.

> MENTAL HEALTH

People from the intervention group experience **comparable levels of psychological well-being and higher levels of mental distress.**

> ECONOMIC WELL-BEING

People from the intervention group experience **widespread unemployment, job insecurity and black/grey work** and describe the opportunity to find a job in the city as not credible or not achievable.

Figure 13: IHW baseline survey results (4).

4. Co-design of visionary and integrated solutions (VIS): bottom-up participative process

4.1. Bottom-up methods and tools used

The co-design of the VIS has been made working in parallel with 2 groups: Las Palmeras neighbours, and the entities of the IN-HUB that might facilitate the co-deployment of the VIS. The entities working in the neighbourhood have joined one or another group depending on the dynamics and topics of each meeting. As both types of actors have a different profile, the participatory process have been adapted to their capacities and skills. To optimize the participation of the group of neighbours, a participatory empowerment methodology has been used, while with the second group the methods have been focused on activate resources and create synergies.

Each group had had its own dynamics, but continuous bilateral and multilateral feedback meetings have been held to boost interactions and synergies. The involvement of all these stakeholders is considered essential to boost a process that goes beyond IN-HABIT and may be sustainable and autonomous over time. The IN-HABIT team has acted as an intermediary to report, discuss and collect feedback on the different proposals designed by both groups. The proposals of each group have been discussed and validated in the other.

The co-design of the ITP has been based on the premises of the development of an action plan, where actions are proposed based on the current state, desired state and actions needed to achieve the desired change, even if adapted to the needs and specificities of the context.

Steps	Description
Analyse problems	Examine the current situation to identify the main challenges and needs to work on in the neighbourhood: "What are the main problems in Las Palmeras?"
Planning	Describe changes, generate ideas and co-create solutions: "How would we like Las Palmeras to be?" "What concrete actions can we take?"
Means	Identify the existing human and economic resources in Las Palmeras: "What resources can be mobilised in the neighbourhood?"
Implementation	Ensure that the plan can be operational and foresee the challenges linked to the execution of the actions: "How to put the planned actions into practice?"
Evaluation	Set clear and concrete objectives and indicators to be able to monitor and evaluate the progress made: "How to know if the actions are effective?"

The working method in each group is described next.

4.1.1. Bottom-up co-design methods in Las Palmeras

The fragmentation and the problems of coexistence in Las Palmeras have required to work in different stages to create trust among the participants and an initial feeling of group or community. The co-design of VIS has been addressed in 3 different phases that will be described next:

1. A pilot study with a reduced number of participants to test the adequacy of the working method.
2. The selection of the participants in this group.
3. The enlargement of the group.

Once the pilot experience has been positively evaluated, the co-design activities have been extended at the neighbourhood level. The process of consolidating the working group and engagement methodology has been accompanied by meetings and bilateral and multilevel workshops. These actions have been monitored and the feedback analysed.

Identification of the pilot group process (April-May 2021)

To identify the pilot group, previous work has been done to detect the level of coexistence and co-management in the different tower blocks in the neighbourhood (from March to May 2021). The main aim of this first process has been to test the level of maturity in participation and organization in all the buildings of the 5 Patios.

Participation is essential to boost a process of transformation. In a neighbourhood, the community participation is exhibited in terms of organization and management of common spaces and in the belonging identity of its neighbours. In Las Palmeras case, the smallest community unit -after the family nucleus- where actions might be taken is the tower block, the next unit would be the patio, and successively the wider communities would be the neighbourhood itself and the city.

Figure 14: Sequence of improvement.

The objective of this first stage has been to assess the participation skills in the organization, management and administration of the community units of the blocks (degree of coexistence, division of tasks, decision making, capacity for conflict resolution, etc.). These elements have not only offered a deeper understanding of the neighbours as a community, but also of their participation and leadership capacities and so, of being involved in a transformation process.

At this stage, the project team visited the families of one tower block from each of the 5 courtyards. The choice of these blocks has been made with the support and knowledge of social services workers and their previous work experience with the community.

Patio	Vicente Sereno	Aneto	Veleta	Almanzor	Mulhacen
Block number	11	1	3	8	10

The work with these participants was organised around the problems of their building community and following Figure 15 sequence that starts with the positive aspects. Weekly meetings were guided by project members in order to monitor the groups and their willingness to be incorporated in the future actions proposed in this ITP. These meetings made possible to evaluate the participation skills in the 5 groups (capacity for mediation, community work, level of commitment, capacity, and willingness to collaborate and share common goals or achieving short common objectives).

Figure 15: Sequence of participation.

Figure 16: Workshops held in the neighbourhood.

After this first assessment of the level of coexistence and organizational capacity and commitment of each of the 5 blocks, the group of 11th block of Vicente Sereno Patio was considered as the most mature to participate in the pilot study for the ITP.

Pilot Study (June-October 2021)

The pilot study aimed to test the viability of the method and tools chosen; to consolidate the knowledge acquired about the context; to reinforce the participation of the core group engaged; to encourage the participation of new actors; to enhance the participation and involvement of the neighbours in improving coexistence and social life in the neighbourhood; to help to create a pleasant environment; to improve the knowledge on environment and social relations; and to detect people interested to participate in IN-HABIT.

To achieve these objectives VMOSA technique have been used in these weekly workshops focused on the health and wellbeing dimensions of IN-HABIT. This phase has also made possible to define how to work on the different dimensions of health and wellbeing with activities that are attractive and based on responses to real needs. Indeed, workshops with neighbours have been hosted to improve self-care, motivation and confidence; participation in decision-making and knowledge acquisition; organization of actions with a common goal, creating a neighbourhood committee; and running co-design workshops on the thematic areas of intervention.

Figure 17: VMOSA methodology.

IN-HUB Co-design workshops (November-December 2021)

Once the work methodology was validated through piloting, the VIS co-design workshops open to the entire neighbourhood have initiated. The workshops have followed Figure 18 structure, even if adapted to the groups and work objectives:

4.1.2. Bottom-up co-design methods with the IN-HUB participants (November 2021-February 2022)

The methodology used to reinforce the participatory process with the different IN-HUB participants has been based on holding different bilateral and multilateral meetings. During the months of November-February there have been constant meetings with entities from the 5 working areas. In these meetings, potential VIS that give answer to Las Palmeras needs and expectations were discussed with entities that have the knowledge, resources, or expertise to make them possible. An initial action plan was drafted including how to develop the VIS, the timing, the costs, the resources needed, and the contribution of each of the actors involved.

Figure 18: Workshops structure.

4.2. Co-design workshops

Once described the methods, this section presents the different workshops hosted in each of the phases, and their objectives and outcomes.

4.2.1. Pilot study workshops (May-October 2021)

The pilot bottom-up co-design workshops have been held weekly during the months of May and June 2021. The group of neighbours involved have been informed through the delivery of a door-to-door invitation and a project brochure, a week before each of them, and in person the morning before the afternoon activities.

These first weekly meetings aimed to explore the most effective ways of addressing wellbeing and mental health in the specific context of Las Palmeras. In this sense, how to involve people in basic forms of renaturation, mental wellbeing workshops and cultural visits have been explored. Issues such as the benefits of gardening for mental health, the properties of seasonal vegetables and aromatic plants and healthy habits such as a balanced diet, have been analysed as transversal topics. Empowerment has also been worked on, reinforcing the importance of active

participation and self-leading role among the participants. It follows a description of these workshops and the objectives, or the values worked in each of them.

4.2.1.1. Basic gardening training to boost healthy habits and mental wellbeing (May-June 2021)

These workshops have had as objectives to familiarise participants with gardening and greening and to learn how to cultivate some edible plants. In these two months basic notions of gardening have been worked on as seedling, planting and transplanting plants, cultivation calendar, irrigation needs, sun exposure, etc...

The most significant outcome has been the creation of “transportable garden boxes” in which seeds of seasonal vegetables and aromatic plants have been sown in boxes. The boxes were placed in the inner patio of one of the buildings, where the participants could make the follow-up.

Figure 19: Transplanting workshops with neighbours.

This physical activity has also been used to work on values. In the activity of transplanting, each participant has been asked to ‘sow a value’ in harmony with the objectives of IN-HABIT, in a figurative way (Figure 19). They have committed to ‘cultivate this value’, at the time they cultivate the plants, as part of this transformative process.

In other workshop, diversity values have been worked by using local and tropical seeds. Each seed has a different shape, might be smaller or larger, rough or smoother, but all of them protect the essence of plants and might give flowers or fruits. In this sense, participants have reflected on the value and uniqueness of each of the participants and on the role of diversity, as essential aspects of this ITP.

4.2.1.2. Instinctive dance workshop (1st of July 2021)

Women in Las Palmeras have very little opportunities to do physical exercise or body care activities. The instinctive dance workshop has allowed to explore how to work on mental health through music, dance, body expression, meditation, and the use of aromas.

4.2.1.3. From the current state to the desired state workshops, (July-September 2021)

These workshops aimed to investigate the perception of people on their own neighbourhood, the desire for change and the willingness to get involved in a plan to transform it. In this sense, it has been essential to emphasize that what participants do is not for the sake of the project, but to have a better live in the area. The pilot study has allowed exploring the possibilities of cultural adaptation of methodological tools, such us the mentioned VMOSA, to the context of Las Palmeras.

In these workshops, the participants have been invited to reflect on a mission that bonds this group, through shared vision and goals:

- Mission: Palmeras green and united.
- Vision: Collaborate to build a better neighbourhood, with the aim of encourage values such as coexistence, respect, security, and cleanliness.

After having agreed on the common objectives, participants assessed the current state of the neighbourhood, analysing the resources that exist, what is missing and what can be improved. Using the map of Las Palmeras, the neighbours have been invited to mentally "walk" through

Figure 21: Assessment of the neighbourhood.

Figure 20: Dance workshop.

their neighbourhood answering these questions and putting some tags of different colours to define the different parts: What do you like of your neighbourhood? What can be improved? What is missing? They were invited to think in people, resources, activities, areas, spaces... The main outcomes have been to give answer to these questions, as follows:

THINGS THEY LIKE				
Sport Club	NGOs support	Estrella Azahara work	Social Services workers	Sport events
MISSING THINGS				
Green areas	Community areas with shade	Cooking course	Activities for elderly people	Fitness room for dance salsa and bachata
Refill empty tree areas	Dogs' area	Football field	Bus stop with walls	Outdoor sport area for exercise
		Urban gardens		
THINGS TO IMPROVE				
Picnic area	Children play areas	More bins	The infrastructure of buildings and common areas	

Figure 22: Result of the assessment.

This first phase has been important to create a core working group, to validate the chosen methodological tools and to adapt them to the context. Also, to explore the specific needs and interests of the inhabitants in actively participating in the ITP. After these pilot workshops that were used to create networks, build trust and create a sense of belonging to the project, more focused VIS co-design workshops have been developed.

Thanks to the experience of the pilot workshops, the lines of work and the dissemination channels to the rest of the neighbourhood have been designed and validated together with the core group:

- Evaluation of pilot activities with proposal for improvement.
- Selection of the working areas and cultural adaptation of the methodological tools.
- Co-design of diffusion methods and of the flyer for the co-design workshops of the VIS open to the entire neighbourhood.

4.2.2. Co-design workshops (November 2021-February 2022)

Since November, weekly workshops with members of the IN-HUB, neighbours, and institutions from Las Palmeras have been run focused on the co-design of the VIS that are part of this ITP.

4.2.2.1. Co-design workshops in Las Palmeras Square (November-December 2021)

The first co-design workshop has been run in the main square at the launch of the IN-HUB in Las Palmeras (as mentioned in section 2.3).

Figure 23: Launch in Las Palmeras.

After a brief introduction describing the project and with the support of experts, inhabitants were asked to brainstorm possible proposals to improve the neighbourhood organised around the 3 following areas: Healthy lifestyle; Art, culture and infrastructures; and Naturalization and environment. Participants identified both current state and needs and were invited to mark them in posters.

From this session a work group have emerged for each area. But they finally have decided to work together, at least initially, because the proposed goals were very interrelated. They have joined efforts for common objectives, working across the different areas to create synergies, reinforcing the core group and encouraging the participation of new neighbours.

The 10th of November, the 3 groups decided that the first VIS to co-deploy together should be the transformation of Las Palmeras central square, fixing as a short term first objective to celebrate a Christmas party. The main objective has been promoting wellbeing through refurbishing and greening of the area and giving it a cultural identity (reproducing the patterns of city monuments, such as the Mosque), to create a healthier, nicer and safer environment.

From this first meeting, weekly workshops to co-deploy this VIS have been held. The results of this action are described in Section 5.

4.2.2.2. Co-design workshop with IN-HUB members (3rd of November 2021)

At the IN-HUB launch (see section 2.3), a co-design workshop was held with the 51 participants. The workshop has been divided into two stages. In the first one, participants were invited to decide in which of the 5 areas of intervention they want to be involved and their level of involvement. In the second one, they were asked on the resources (human-social capital, knowledge, expertise, funding) they could contribute (Figure 24 displays both results).

Figure 24: Workshop result.

This meeting has allowed to:

- Consolidate the connection of entities with the IN-HABIT project by reinforcing the engagement processes of the IN-HUB.
- Establish the basis to create synergies and collaboration between different entities.
- Knowing more in-depth the social and human capital.
- Attracting the attention of Cordoba's entities to the needs and expectations of Las Palmeras.

4.2.2.3. Co-design workshop with IN-HUB members (3rd of December 2021)

Figure 25: Workshops with entities.

Several IN-HUB participants were invited to this workshop that was hosted in the premises of Las Palmeras Civic Centre. Seventeen people from 13 entities attended. For most of them was the first time they visit the neighbourhood. The workshop aimed to further elaborate on the proposals drafted at the IN-HUB launch and to analyse how they could be co-deployed. It was a significant step in the developing of this ITP, laying the

foundations of the delicate transition from co-design to co-deployment. Proposals for concrete actions were collected to develop a short-term co-designed action plan with activities that could be developed in the next 6 months.

Two parallel work groups were run to identify possible VIS, and synergies, human-social capital, knowledge and expertise. These groups worked on:

- Gender, Diversity, inclusion and Social Innovation and Culture, Heritage and Art;
- Health and Wellbeing and Naturalization and Environment.

Very relevant insights from the group of Gender, Diversity, Inclusion and Social Innovation were the need to bear in mind that structural problems in Las Palmeras such as absenteeism and school failure, unemployment, gender violence, social isolation makes it difficult for the population to participate. Additionally, the lack of attachment to the neighbourhood and its facilities make that the inhabitants do not care or even vandalise them. In this sense, the working group agreed

Figure 26: Things to consider.

that soft VIS should focus on long-term education and work with family units and adolescents, even if these are difficult and time and resource consuming processes, often with uncertain outcomes.

From this starting situation, it is agreed that actions must taking special attention to the actions reflected in Figure 26.

In relation to the group of Health and Wellbeing and Naturalization and Environment, the work dynamic was different, making more concrete VIS proposals that might be carried out in shorter periods of time due to the specificity of the proposals and the context. The main proposals focused on the need to increase green areas, on how involve people on greening, healthy habits proposals and prevention of loneliness, isolation and exclusion. Synergies and collaboration opportunities between different entities emerged.

Regarding the Infrastructure, Technology and Digitalization work group, bilateral work meetings have been held with each of the collaborating entities in this area regarding to the specific and technical characteristics of each proposal.

4.3. Design for Change (DFC) workshops to promote mindset change (September 2021)

The DFC workshops took place between the 6th and the 10th of September 2021. Two workshops with educators, each one of 12 hours, took place at the Foggara Civic centre from Las Palmeras. Almost 40 educators working in Las Palmeras have been involved and trained in the DFC methodology. This methodology, I CAN Mindset, uses the principles of design thinking. This “formula” intentionally cultivates the I CAN Mindset through 5 steps: Feel, Do, Imagine, Evolute (Evaluation+Evolution) and Share.

Design for Change (DFC) is a global movement that cultivates the ‘I CAN’ mindset in children by giving them an opportunity to express their own ideas for a better world and put them into action. Through the simple design process of Feel – Imagine – Do – Share, children identify what bothers them in their communities, imagine how they can make it better, put their ideas into action and share their stories to inspire children around the world to believe that they are NOT helpless, that change is possible, and they CAN drive it.

The workshops introduced design and co-design activities to educators working in educational centres, and social and civil organizations of Las Palmeras, with the aim of providing them co-design tools to help the community (women, children, young people, people with disabilities...) become the primary actor and agent of change within the framework of the IN-HABIT project. Participants were guided by a DFC facilitator through the 5-steps process based on design thinking and trained in the I CAN Mindset tool to develop abilities through challenge-solving. The trained educators will further apply the DFC method and adapt it accordingly to the needs of specific target groups.

The 4 days of workshops have been very well appreciated not only because of the techniques and methodology learned, but also because they have opened the possibility of creating a network of neighbourhood educators. It has been a very important moment of reflection on the needs and opportunities that educators face every day in Las Palmeras. The workshop offered a unique opportunity of coexistence and shared learning.

One of the participating entities has already used the methodology to work with a group of adolescents using these tools to improve their mental wellbeing working with peers. All the entities of the neighbourhood have agreed to work with this methodology on a common theme and to expose all the work developed and the outcomes in an event at Las Palmeras.

5. City-specific VIS to boost IHW

5.1. Planned hard and soft solutions

For each of the working areas a number of hard and soft VIS solutions have been co-designed. Figure 27 shows the methods used. Hard solutions include nature-based innovations, creative and artistic works, infrastructures, smart lighting and monitoring devices that should be co-deployed between months 14-36 of the project. The main aim in Las Palmeras is to naturalize the 5 patios and the central square and transformed them in green and artistic areas. This need and expectation have been expressed in all the co-design workshops. However, neighbours and researchers are afraid that they might be vandalised by those inhabitants not interested in the upgrade of these spaces. As it would be mentioned in the next section, some of the actions already deployed have been damaged or not respected.

Soft solutions include cultural, digital and social innovations that will be co-deployed between months 14-48 of the project and that will support the hard VIS acceptance and maintenance. These will be linked to the tangible and intangible heritage value of patios and their role as eco-social builders to boost inclusive health and wellbeing.

The process to include these VIS in the ITP has been the following:

- Identification of the needs and expectations with the neighbours and Las Palmeras Committee.
- Identification of potential solutions with members of the IN-HUB.

- First check with the neighbours and Las Palmeras Committee of the interest and feasibility of these VIS.
- Fine-tuning of the VIS with members of the IN-HUB and neighbours.
- Final check with the IN-HUB User Advisory Board and Las Palmeras Committee.

The co-deployment is essential to establish the management and organization of the VIS. Given the different nature of the VIS, each action will have its own planning, even if some similar patterns might be followed. The co-management has been determined horizontally, with the participation and involvement of the neighbours, the actors directly interested in each VIS, the guide of the experience of the professional stakeholders and experts in the field and with the mediation of the IN-HABIT team (UCO, AVUE and City Council).

Figure 27: Methodology of the VIS.

5.2. Co-designed VIS

The co-designed VIS that conforms this ITP are listed next. A colour code has been assigned to each working area (green for naturalization and environment; blue for health and wellbeing; yellow for culture, heritage and art; dark blue for gender diversity, inclusion, and social innovation and red for infrastructure, technology and digitalization).

Appendix 8 includes more details of each VIS. Hard VIS are presented in bold colour, and soft VIS in light colour. Additionally, for each of them the stakeholders involved are identified, and the IHW dimensions addressed included. Appendix 3 describes the final stakeholders and main competences to support the related VIS. Finally, the KPIs that might support the monitoring have been incorporated.

HARD VIS

Health and Wellbeing	
	Sport facilities in the neighbourhood
	Public areas as safe playground spaces
Culture, Heritage and Art	
	Artistic creations in patios
	Mobile and fix exhibition furniture
Naturalization and Environment	
	Naturalization of patios (squares)
	Natural ponds
	Urban orchards
	Implement a (permanent) FLORA artistic creation in the neighbourhood
	Therapeutical and inclusive garden
Infrastructure, Technology, and Digitalization	
	Sustainable lighting infrastructures in patios
	Inclusive, friendly and ecological urban furniture in patios
	Hotspots of wi-fi access in patios
	Platform and sensors for environmental monitoring of patios
	Structural and support elements for patios using 3D printing, recycled materials...

SOFT VIS

Health and Wellbeing	
	Healthy habits workshops
	Local sport activities and events
	Sport activities for women and girls
	Self-care and inclusive wellbeing activities
	Healthy low-cost menus
	Business incubation activities
	Periodic radio program

Culture, Heritage and Art

Cultural events
Culture, heritage and arts workshops
Healthy, sustainable and cultural walks
Cultural 'recipes' to improve health and wellbeing
Virtual Museum of Las Palmeras
Activities for the promotion and dissemination of intangible cultural heritage and natural heritage
Flamenco dressing parade
Joint cultural activities between artists from the neighbourhood and the city

Gender, Diversity, Inclusion, and Social Innovation

Las Palmeras Committee
Mindset change activities to promote empowerment and inclusion
Mapping of the talents and abilities of the neighbours
Creation of women safe spaces
Behavioural games
Prevention of violence workshops

Naturalization and Environment

Intangible corridor with Axerquia inhabitants
Training and workshops in natural and gardening care
Training and workshops in floral creations
Training and workshops for recycling and reuse materials
Therapy gardening activities
Celebration of "Los Patios Festival" in the neighbourhood

Infrastructure, Technology, and Digitalization

Training in digital and technological skills
Vocational training on specific jobs
DAO as governance model for patios

5.3. Co-deployment and co-management of VIS

5.3.1. Co-deployment of VIS.

The co-deployment is an essential step in the management and organization of the VIS that will be done with and by the neighbours. Given the different nature of the VIS, each action will have its own planning, even if some similar patterns might be followed. The co-management has been determined horizontally, with the participation and involvement of the neighbours, the actors directly interested in each VIS, the guidance of the professional stakeholders and experts in the

field and with the mediation of the IN-HABIT team (UCO, AVUE and City Council). Once deployed, the VIS will co-managed and co-monitored by Las Palmeras Committee and other interested stakeholders.

Social public procurement practices will be tested, since subcontracting companies will be asked to hire vulnerable people from Las Palmeras to provide them with employment opportunities during the infrastructural works. Training workshops to build the necessary skills in gardening, masonry, painting, carpentry, ICT, etc. are part of the soft VIS proposed. These actions will contribute to build capacities, to address the high unemployment existing in the quarter and to enhance health, wellbeing and inclusion. Equally, they will increase the sense of ownership on the re-designed public spaces.

IN-HABIT will explore innovative governance and co-management models of NBS, social and technological solutions associated with the tangible and intangible heritage value of patios and their role as eco-social builders to boost inclusive health and wellbeing.

As the co-deployment of some VIS have initiated, it follows a short description of them.

5.3.2. Ongoing co-designed VIS

5.3.2.1. ERACIS (Working Group for social and labour insertion in Las Palmeras)

The Regional Strategy for Social Cohesion (ERACIS) is running in parallel with IN-HABIT and developing a Plan for Disadvantaged Areas, with the goal of transform the vision of these areas and promoting the elimination of territory as a factor of exclusion.

IN-HABIT has been fully involved in one of the objectives of the plan: "Dynamization of Neighbourhood Communities and Courtyards". At the same time, it has collaborated in the elaboration of socio-labour itineraries of people from Palmeras. The main difficulties found are the low training and education, the work in the informal economy, the family responsibilities, the existence of social aid that discourages work, or the situation caused by the pandemic.

A searching of the main training and guidance resources for labour insertion in the area has been done (i.e., Orienta, SAE, IMDEEC, Social Services, neighbourhood and social entities...) to explore the possibilities of coordination and joint actions. Some of the needs identified are: information and information sharing; design of low profile courses; creation of a literacy core group to prepare the exams; digital literacy initiatives; demand for courses delivering "useful" training: forklift

driver, driver's license; and courses with hiring commitment; dissemination of success stories on networks or radio; aid or scholarships for transportation to the courses, among others.

5.3.2.2. Talent map

An interactive map with the different talents of the neighbours living in each patio is being elaborated. Each participant can choose the level of visibility of their talent. This tool supports the identification of the human capital existing in Las Palmeras, might publicize the talents existing in the neighbourhood, reducing stigma and self-stigma, empowering inhabitants and underlining the capacities of neighbours to support IN-HABIT VIS.

5.3.2.3. Transformation of the central square in Las Palmeras, Christmas party co-deployment workshops

Figure 28: [Main square before and after intervention \(click here to see the video\).](#)

One of the first deficiencies recognized in the neighbourhood has been the lack of a neutral, safe, green and inclusive space where the ideas of the IN-HUB can be brought to life. Together with the neighbours have been decided that the central square might play this role and a plan to reform it has been designed. An initiative to paint the columns and benches with the colours of Cordoba Mezquita (Mosque, a historical monument of Cordoba and UNESCO heritage site) have been co-designed and co-deployed with the support of entities and neighbours. The

Figure 29: Works in the neighborhood.

short-term objective has been to prepare part of the square to be a welcoming space to celebrate the Christmas party for the entire neighbourhood.

With this idea, weekly workshops have been run on mental wellbeing and healthy habits, art and cultural heritage and re-naturalisation with neighbours, associations and schools. As a result, different VIS were co-deployed:

- painting the columns and benches with typical colours;
- gardening workshops;
- planting climbing plants that can recreate the white and red arch with their flowers;
- aromatic candles crafting with smell of typical plants of Cordoba workshops and
- Christmas decoration under the motto "The hands that lift the neighbourhood", made by the kids in which each one has written their commitment to improve the neighbourhood.

Symbolically, to start this regeneration process, [a native tree has been planted \(click here to see the video\)](#). Once redecorated this part of the square a Christmas party was organised with traditional local Christmas songs and dances and the performance of Nativity scenes with children. The celebration of this Christmas party was conceived as a concrete visualization of the process carried out by the neighbours and the neighbourhood from the creation of the IN-HUB, both by other inhabitants and by Cordoba inhabitants, since a lot of them had been invited to the event. Unfortunately, a new wave of COVID restricted the number of assistants and only people from Las Palmeras assisted. In any case, its celebration acted as a point of union and synergy between the different associations.

Figure 30: Workshop posters.

5.3.2.4. Inclusive, healthy and cultural walks.

Every 4-6 weeks is planned a visit to one cultural site or event, with inhabitants from both Las Palmeras and Axerquia, using sustainable mobility means or walking, when possible, to experiment the health benefits of exercising. As far as now, the first of these walks have been organised:

Guided visit to the international IV FLORA Festival edition, the 15th of October 2021. This edition was dedicated to "The Force". The pandemic has changed many things, possibly more than we can now detect, and the festival wanted to make a wake-up call to the power that nature brings us to face the new times. Several inhabitants from las Palmeras visited the five floral exhibitions accompanied by a guide. People travelled on public bus to and from the festival.

Figure 31: Flora Festival visit.

Unfortunately, once again the COVID situation did not permit other visits. The next one is planned for the 4th of March 2022 to the Cordoba's Botanical Garden and will be used as an initial demonstration of the natural ponds that will be co-deployed.

5.3.2.5. Safe Space for women (Purple Point)

A safe space for women has been created responding to the demands they have expressed in different workshops and interviews. Women are the pillar of the family units in Las Palmeras and often, violence and gender discrimination are diffused. Issues such as insecurity, loneliness, and struggle as a woman, have also come up.

For these reasons, this space has been created and 2 workshops (10 participants each) have been already run to decide the topic that they want to discuss (meditation, communication skills, empowerment, ...).

In the workshops the most important topics that the women decided to share have been:

<i>Frustration</i>	<i>Wellbeing of the children</i>
<i>Feeling accompanied</i>	<i>I would like to know each other better from inside</i>
<i>What to do to live well?</i>	<i>Limit between city and self-care</i>
<i>What does it mean to be a woman in Las Palmeras?</i>	<i>Tired of fighting so hard</i>

All of them have been asked to reflect on their own values as a person and as a woman. Each one has shared the values that they can share in the group:

“I am worth because....”	
<i>Listening ability</i>	<i>I’m trusted</i>
<i>I am educated</i>	<i>Optimistic</i>
<i>I’m friend</i>	<i>Good mother</i>
<i>I’m a good person</i>	<i>Disinterested</i>

5.3.2.6. Monthly IN-HABIT Radio Program

There is a radio station, Onda Palmeras, emitting periodically from Las Palmeras. As part of the communication and dissemination plan, IN-HABIT has participated in its programs and sessions with researchers and members of the IN-HUB have been recorded. However, from February 2021, IN-HABIT has its own monthly session, “Palmeras tu voz se oye” (Palmeras your voice is heard), which has been co-designed as is done with the neighbours.

Figure 32: Recording of the radio program.

The program aims to work in several aspects: exercise the right of communication in this institutionally ignored neighbourhood; boost an active role of the neighbours in providing contents, making decisions, promoting participation, etc.; promoting the development of empowerment capabilities and awareness raising of their potentialities; being an informative channel of the project activities at the neighbourhood and city levels.

5.4. Analysis of the impact of changes proposed

The ITP is conceived as an open and continuous process. In this sense after the first proposal of 44 VIS, a second feedback and adjustment has been done for each action (following the co-design of VIS process describe in D1.1. pag. 43, fig. 18), based on the constant changes of the real and urgent needs of the context and on the external constrains (for example to consider the tree planting season or the bureaucratic procedures...).

For this reason, following our co-deployment and co-management approach, further co-design workshops have been held to define in a more appropriate and contextualized way the implementation of the IN-HUB proposals.

All the VIS needs to be adapted to the skills, aptitudes, and knowledge of the target population and for that, as already mentioned, the soft VIS have been prioritized. As explained in the initial sections of this document, Covid-19 and the specific difficulties of the context made it necessary to deploy adapted strategies for participation in IN-HABIT actions, and in Cordoba, to put the focus in soft VIS that can enhance the success possibilities of hard VIS. After the initial deliverable was submitted, the VIS deployment has considerable accelerated, and the next paragraphs reflect some of these changes.

In this sense, 23 different specific actions have been planned to be carried out from December 2021 to May 2023.

Table 1 displays the development and results of the initial VISs, after being adapted in the first round of IN-HUB proposals. The VIS ID* refers to the corresponding number of VIS elaborated in the previous co-design workshops and reflected in Annex 8, meanwhile TARGET GROUP** refers to the groups with protected characteristics on which the project in Córdoba focuses its action. These are young people, women, LGBTQI+ people, people with disabilities, families (included those with small children), elderly people and ethnic and religious minorities. Additionally, it includes the IHW subdimension that the actions aim to boost and the KPI (as included in the Grant Agreement) that will be used to measure the impact. The last column includes the stakeholders in charge of the management of the actions, but others will be invited to get involved in them during the co-design and co-deployment of the actions.

ACTION	VIS ID*	DESCRIPTION	TIME	OBJECTIVES	IHW SUB-DIMENSION	KPI (reflected in GA)	TARGET VALUE	TARGET GROUP**	STAKEHOLDERS
Christmas Workshops	2B.1 2B.2 3B.6 4B.2	Workshops carried out with the neighbours to prepare the Christmas Party and decorate the central square during Christmas. Implementation of joint actions between neighbours, schools and entities for the preparation of the neighbourhood Christmas party and its decoration.	Nov-Dec 2021	Elaborate the decoration of the central square for the Christmas party. Establish joint work dynamics between entities and associations and the project. Promote joint and inclusive work in a context of exclusion to increase wellbeing.	Cultural participation Determinants of health Equality Social inclusion Crime/security and violence / Physical health status Employment / Leisure and free time	Number of inclusive activities developed	2	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ Neighbours ▪ Bosque Anxanar
						Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption	80	20	
						Number of spaces for art production & exhibition	2	2	
						Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	100	50	
Central square rehabilitation	2B.1 2B.2 4A.1 5A.2	Actions carried out to decorate and rehabilitate the central square of las Palmeras. Painting benches and columns of the pergola, as well as the plantation of a tree and some plants.	Nov-Dec 2021	Rehabilitate the central square of the neighbourhood from the co-design with the neighbours and through community actions. Establish joint work dynamics between entities and associations and the project.	Cultural participation Determinants of health Spatial wellbeing	M2 of new accessible green space created	50m2	50m2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ AVUE ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ Neighbours ▪ Bosque Anxanar
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	2	2	
						Number of spaces for art production & exhibition	1	1	
						Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	70	30	
Christmas Party	2A.1 2B.1 2B.2 2B.6 3B.1	Celebration of a Christmas Party as the final event of the work carried out during November and December. All entities and associations from the neighbourhood have collaborated with the organization and development of the event.	Dec 2021	Celebrate cultural and social events in the Las Palmeras neighbourhood. Establish joint work dynamics between entities and associations and the project. Promote joint and inclusive work in a context of exclusion to increase wellbeing.	Cultural participation Determinants of health Social inclusion	Number of inclusive activities developed	1	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ AVUE ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ Neighbours ▪ Bosque Anxanar
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	1	1	
						Number of spaces for art production & exhibition	1	1	
						Creative festivals and fairs	1	1	
						Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	120	60	

ACTION	VIS ID*	DESCRIPTION	TIME	OBJECTIVES	IHW SUB-DIMENSION	KPI (reflected in GA)	TARGET VALUE	TARGET GROUP**	STAKEHOLDERS
Carnival Party	2B.1 2B.2 2B.6 3B.1	Celebration of the Carnival in the neighbourhood with children from all associations, schools, and entities as a way of giving access to the people to events celebrated in the city, but not in the neighbourhood. Games in each patio and different activities carried out, as well as a healthy snack given to each participant.	Feb 2022	Celebrate cultural and social events in the Las Palmeras neighbourhood. Promote joint and inclusive work in a context of exclusion to increase wellbeing. Energize the children of the neighbourhood with playful actions that encourage their involvement and improve their vision of the neighbourhood, also involving family members.	Cultural participation Determinants of health Social inclusion	Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	100	60	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ Neighbours
						Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption	250	160	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	1	1	
						Creative festivals and fairs	1	1	
Women day (March 8 th)	1B.2 1B.3 2B.1 2B.6 3B.1 3B.4	Collaboration with the painting of the mural "Palmeras with female voice". Each part is painted by a woman of the neighbourhood. Collaboration with entities (Red XXI and Estrella Azahara) to celebrate the Women Day through the celebration of a women football match, sport mostly played by men. This match will be played by female educators against mothers and sister of the participants in the activities of each entity.	Mar 2022	Celebrate cultural and social events in the Las Palmeras neighbourhood. Claim the role of women in society and in the labour and social world. Make visible the role of women in sport and their potential. Fight against stereotypes of women in the neighbourhood and empower women from different groups.	Sports practice Leisure and free time Equality Cultural participation Determinants of health Social inclusion Discrimination	Number of persons by PCs participating in sport activities	300	200	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ Neighbours ▪ ERACIS
						Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	150	125	
						Number of inclusive activities developed	2	2	
						Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption	225	155	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	2	2	
						Activities for the promotion of new roles for women (innovators, scientists, entrepreneurs)	2	2	

ACTION	VIS ID*	DESCRIPTION	TIME	OBJECTIVES	IHW SUB-DIMENSION	KPI (reflected in GA)	TARGET VALUE	TARGET GROUP**	STAKEHOLDERS
Inclusive congress organization	1B.6	Collaboration of the Congress "Asset our Impact" organised by CUCO. The people responsible for supporting the event all of them have some type of disability or functional limitation, betting on employability and inclusiveness in collective events.	Mar 2022	Promote inclusive actions and activities in the social context of Córdoba from the point of view of employability and empowerment, betting on adaptability and the inclusion of diversity.	Employment Job and skills satisfaction	Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	25	25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UCO CUCO Cordoba Down
						Number of inclusive activities developed	2	2	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	2	2	
May Cross	2B.1 2B.2 2B.6 2B.8 3B.1 4B.3 4B.4 5A.5	Celebration of one of the most important festivals in Córdoba in the neighbourhood of Palmeras, excluded for years from this event. This event has been linked to the celebration of more than 6 workshops of more than 3 hours each for co-design and co-deployment, all of them carried out by the residents of the neighbourhood.	Apr 2022	Celebrate cultural and social events in the Las Palmeras neighbourhood. Create work dynamics and make the neighbours responsible for different actions of social transformation and revitalization. Promote cultural actions as a form of social wellbeing and health.	Cultural participation Determinants of health Social cohesion Social inclusion Employment / Leisure and free time Financial situation /	Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	150	80	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UCO Palmeras Committee Neighbours El Brote
						Number of inclusive activities developed	5	5	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	1	1	
						Number of spaces for art production & exhibition	1	1	
						Creative festivals and fairs	1	1	
Absenteeism prevention event	3B.1	Collaboration in the organization of an event to recognize high school graduates from the Las Palmeras neighbourhood and the creation of a mural to promote study and prevent absenteeism.	May 2022	Promote schooling, completion of studies and enrolment in higher education. Give visibility to people in the neighbourhood who have finished the secondary education.	Social inclusion	Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	50	40	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UCO AVUE Palmeras Committee Neighbours Absenteeism Committee
						Number of inclusive activities developed	1	1	
Patio's cleaning	4A.1	Carrying out a cleaning of the Vicente Sereno patio with the neighbours of this patio, supported by the municipal cleaning company.	Jun 2022	Promote actions focused on each patio as a way of dynamization and empowerment. Clean the patios as a joint action and a way to vindicate the state of abandonment of the neighbourhood.	Spatial wellbeing	Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	30	30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UCO Neighbours

ACTION	VIS ID*	DESCRIPTION	TIME	OBJECTIVES	IHW SUB-DIMENSION	KPI (reflected in GA)	TARGET VALUE	TARGET GROUP**	STAKEHOLDERS
Socio-cultural workshops with neighbours	1B.4 2B.1 2B.6	Initial round of workshops with the neighbours to work on culture, the social context of the neighbourhood and specific actions to be developed in each area.	Jan-Jul 2022	Develop actions of a sociocultural nature in the neighbourhood with the neighbours. Launch actions and activities that improve the mental health and wellbeing of the neighbours and the neighbourhood through sociocultural actions and resources.	Positive emotions / Physical health status Cultural participation Determinants of health	Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	100	60	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ Neighbours
						Food education initiatives	2	2	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	3	3	
						Activities for the promotion of new roles for women (innovators, scientists, entrepreneurs)	2	2	
Mental health and social wellbeing workshops	1B.1 1B.4	Initial round of workshops with the neighbours to work on the mental and emotional health of each one, with different actions in relation to health and well-being as a way of applying the indicators and sub-indicators established for Córdoba.	Jan-Jul 2022	Develop actions to promote healthy habits and mental health in the neighbourhood with the neighbours. Launch actions and activities that improve the mental health and wellbeing of the neighbours and the neighbourhood through co-design.	Determinants of health Positive emotions / Physical health status	Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	100	60	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ Neighbours
						Number of inclusive activities developed	10	10	
						Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption	220	120	
Sociocultural walks	1B.4 2B.3 2B.6	Monthly walks to visit artistic and cultural events in the city will be organised to help Las Palmeras inhabitants to rediscover Córdoba's culture and heritage. These shared experiences aim to reinforce the belonging to the city and the feeling of community; to cultivate the values of respect for the natural and build environment and to	Oct 2021 -On	Promote health through healthy walks around the city. Show the hidden patrimony of the city. Reinforce the feeling of belonging to the city.	Positive emotions / Physical health status Cultural participation Leisure and free time Determinants of health; Cultural participation	Number of inclusive activities developed	10	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ AVUE ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ Neighbours ▪ INGEMA ▪ FLORA Festival
						Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption	180	80	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	10	10	

ACTION	VIS ID*	DESCRIPTION	TIME	OBJECTIVES	IHW SUB-DIMENSION	KPI (reflected in GA)	TARGET VALUE	TARGET GROUP**	STAKEHOLDERS
		appreciating the importance of caring for it.				Activities for the promotion of new roles for women (innovators, scientists, entrepreneurs)	4	4	
Periodic radio program	1B.7	An IN-HABIT periodic radio program (once a month for the moment) is running from January 2021 in Las Palmeras Radio Station. Inhabitants, stakeholders, and researchers participate to disseminate news of the project and encourage people to take an active role in the transformation of the neighbourhood. The program is also used to boost empowerment, improve participation and communication skills and promote participation in the project activities.	Oct 2021 -On	Disseminate and promote IN-HABIT actions to the rest of the city and the neighbourhood through the radio program. Empower neighbours to participate and disseminate their actions in the neighbourhood.	Social cohesion Social inclusion / Leisure and free time	Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	30	20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ Neighbours ▪ Red XXI
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	10	10	
						Activities for the promotion of new roles for women (innovators, scientists, entrepreneurs)	5	5	
Baila mi barrio / Dance my Neighbourhood	2B.1 2B.2 3B.1 3B.2	<p>Video dance carried out with the collaboration of neighbours and artistic direction (choreographer, professional dancers...).</p> <p>3 sessions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ work sessions for learning choreography with neighbours of Palmeras. ▪ shooting with the neighbours in locations of the neighbourhood. ▪ Presentation of Acieloabierto network show and premiere screening of video-dance. 	Oct-Dec 2022	Promote physical and mental health through dance. Promote social welfare through social inclusion and fight against isolation and stigma through a different visual perspective towards the neighbourhood and the connection with the rest of the city, offered by the possibility of projecting the video recorded in different places.	Cultural participation Determinants of health Social inclusion Discrimination Equality	Number of persons by PCs participating in sport activities	20	20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ Choreographer ▪ Dancers ▪ Neighbours
						Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	50	30	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	3	3	
						Number of spaces for art production & exhibition	2	2	

ACTION	VIS ID*	DESCRIPTION	TIME	OBJECTIVES	IHW SUB-DIMENSION	KPI (reflected in GA)	TARGET VALUE	TARGET GROUP**	STAKEHOLDERS
						Activities for the promotion of new roles for women (innovators, scientists, entrepreneurs)	3	3	
Renaturalization of Palmeras	3B.4 4A.1 4B.2 4A.5 5A.2	Repopulate the green areas of the neighbourhood (selection of trees; sponsorship; plantation; taking neighbourhood care...): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Main square: 31 pits for vine/climbing plants. Courtyard Vicente Sereno: 23 big pits and 79 small pits. 	Nov 2022 -Dec-2023	Repopulate existing empty spaces for trees and plants. Make Palmeras a greener space. Empower people to take care of their neighbourhood and respect vegetation and improvements.	Discrimination Spatial wellbeing Employment / Leisure and free time Social inclusion Equality Spatial wellbeing	M2 of new accessible green space created	600m2	600m2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UCO AVUE Palmeras Committee Neighbours El Brote
						M2 of therapy gardens	200m2	200m2	
						M2 of organic food growing initiatives	500m2	500m2	
						M2 of community gardens	100m2	100m2	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	10	10	
						Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	100	60	
						Number of inclusive activities developed	10	10	
Rest area and green corridor	3B.4 4A.1 4A.5 5A.2	Create urban green areas equipped for leisure, rest, sports, and healthy activities. Design and install of sustainable urban furniture and urban equipment, as well as urban orchards.	May 2023	Increase green areas of the neighbourhood. Create a green space to walk through with shadow, less temperature and urban facilities.	Equality / Discrimination Spatial wellbeing Social inclusion	M2 of new accessible green space created	600m2	600m2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UCO AVUE Palmeras Committee Neighbours El Brote
						M2 of community gardens	100m2	100m2	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	5	5	
						Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	150	35	
						Number of inclusive activities developed	5	5	

ACTION	VIS ID*	DESCRIPTION	TIME	OBJECTIVES	IHW SUB-DIMENSION	KPI (reflected in GA)	TARGET VALUE	TARGET GROUP**	STAKEHOLDERS
						Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption	350	125	
Rehabilitation of Cantarranas Stream	3B.4 4A.1 4A.5 5A.2	Recover the stream that is part of the landscape heritage of the Real Cañada del Guadalquivir to create a point of natural observation and research area and environmental education (flora/fauna typical of the stream area) space.	Sept 2022 -Dec 2023	Recover existing natural spaces in the neighbourhood. Create a space for observation and protection of nature. Value the location of the neighbourhoods and the diversity that exists in it.	Equality / Discrimination Spatial wellbeing Social inclusion Equality Spatial wellbeing	M2 of new accessible green space created	2500m2	2500m2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ AVUE ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ Neighbours ▪ El Brote
						M2 of community gardens	200m2	200m2	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	4	4	
						Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	60	40	
						Number of inclusive activities developed	10	10	
Las Palmeras through the lens of the neighbours	2B.1 2B.2 2B.5 2B.6 3B.2	Photography workshop to design neighbourhood improvement points through the image-space relationship and emotions. Define through the photo workshop, which are the spaces that do make locals feel good or bad, work on the reason for these emotions and identify positive elements for mental health that can be replicated and spaces that make people feel bad and improve.	Jan-Feb 2023	Analyse the vision that the residents have of their neighbourhood. Point the areas where an intervention is needed in the neighbourhood. Work on expressions, emotions, emotional intelligence, and social skills. Teach the participants how to use a camera and the possibilities it has to create new visions and interpretations of the reality.	Cultural participation Determinants of health Social cohesion Social inclusion Discrimination Equality	Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	40	25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ AVUE ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ Neighbours ▪ Red XXI ▪ Estrella Azahara
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	4	4	
						Creative festivals and fairs	1	1	
						Activities for the promotion of new roles for women (innovators, scientists, entrepreneurs)	2	2	
						Number of inclusive activities developed	2	2	

ACTION	VIS ID*	DESCRIPTION	TIME	OBJECTIVES	IHW SUB-DIMENSION	KPI (reflected in GA)	TARGET VALUE	TARGET GROUP**	STAKEHOLDERS
Photo contest and photo exhibition with installation in a popular space in the city	2B.1 2B.2 2B.5 2B.6	Invite the neighbourhood to a photo contest with different categories. The best photos will be installed in a representative space of the city centre and visitors will be asked to share their views and impressions (before / after).	Feb-Jun 2023	Work on the social visibility of the neighbourhood. Break down the architectural and social barriers that separate the neighbourhood from the rest of the city.	Cultural participation Determinants of health Social cohesion Social inclusion	Number of spaces for art production & exhibition	1	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UCO AVUE Palmeras Committee Official photographer
						Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	25	15	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	1	1	
						Creative festivals and fairs	1	1	
						Activities for the promotion of new roles for women (innovators, scientists, entrepreneurs)	1	1	
						Number of inclusive activities developed	1	1	
Food and healthy habits	1B.1 1B.4 1B.5	Implementation of workshops to increase the healthy habits of the neighbours related with food and nutrition, through the collaboration with experts and professionals.	Feb-May 2023	Work healthy lifestyle habits. Work food and nutrition from the reality of each neighbour. Adapt a healthy diet to the possibilities of each one.	Determinants of health Positive emotions Physical health status Financial situation	Number of inclusive activities developed	10	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UCO Palmeras Committee Mercacor-doba Researchers from the UCO Medicine Faculty
						Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	100	50	
						Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption	180	80	
						Food education initiatives	4	4	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	3	3	

ACTION	VIS ID*	DESCRIPTION	TIME	OBJECTIVES	IHW SUB-DIMENSION	KPI (reflected in GA)	TARGET VALUE	TARGET GROUP**	STAKEHOLDERS
Leisure and healthy habits	1B.1 1B.2 1B.4	Development of workshops and activities to create new habits related with leisure, sports practice, hobbies... and give the neighbours the opportunity to develop new tools to use their time.	Feb-Dec 2023	Work healthy lifestyle habits. Develop new forms of entertainment and use of free time. Encourage the performance of sport and physical activity as part of a healthy life and value its contribution to wellbeing.	Physical health status Determinants of health Sports practice Leisure and free time Positive emotions / Physical health status	Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	80	50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ AVUE ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ Neighbours ADSAM ▪ RED XXI ▪ Estrella Azahara ▪ Sports UCO ▪ IMDECO
						Number of inclusive activities developed	10	10	
						Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption	220	165	
						Number of persons by PCs participating in sport activities	40	30	
						Food education initiatives	2	2	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	4	4	
Renovation and installation of urban infrastructures	1A.1 1A.2 4A.1	Renovation and installation of urban infrastructure needed to carry out the project with the collaboration of the City Hall such as water access point to take care of new trees or installation of new recycling points and bins, benches...	Feb-May 2023	Recover the deteriorated infrastructure of the neighbourhood. Create new dynamics in municipal management. Implement the means to be able to develop new actions.	Sports practice Leisure and free time Spatial wellbeing	M2 of new accessible green space created	1200m2	1200m2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ AVUE ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ City Hall
						M2 of therapy gardens	100m2	100m2	
						M2 of organic food growing initiatives	200m2	200m2	
						M2 of community gardens	100m2	100m2	
						Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	5	5	
						Number of spaces for art production & exhibition	2	2	
						Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	80	35	

ACTION	VIS ID*	DESCRIPTION	TIME	OBJECTIVES	IHW SUB-DIMENSION	KPI (reflected in GA)	TARGET VALUE	TARGET GROUP**	STAKEHOLDERS
Sport activities	1B.1 1B.2 1B.3 3B.4	Implementation, promotion, and support of sports actions, as well as collaboration in the management and development of sports events in the Las Palmeras neighbourhood in order to promote a healthy lifestyle, specially for women that have no offer. It is intended to specifically highlight the role of women in sport.	Jan-Dec 2023	Promote the creation and implementation of sports initiatives, especially for women.	Physical health status Determinants of health Sports practice Leisure and free time Equality Sport practice Discrimination	Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups	10	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UCO ▪ Palmeras Committee ▪ City Hall ▪ AVUE ▪ Neighbourhoods ▪ ADSAM ▪ Red XXI ▪ Estrella Azahara ▪ La Milla
				Make visible the role of women in sport.		Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities	650	200	
				Support in the management and implementation of sports actions.		Number of persons by PCs participating in sport activities	3550	1250	
				Promote a healthy lifestyle through sport.		Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption	1200	200	

After having co-designed the VIS with the Cordoba IN-HUB, the causal bonds connecting the solutions to the expected changes and Key Impact Indicators derived from the co-designed list of the VIS for the city of Cordoba (see Annex 4 of D7.3) have been established, in collaboration with WP7 Leader (ISIMPACT). Each solution responds to a precise need to increase health and well-being in the inhabitants of the neighbourhood. Table 2 displays for each solution the expected changes and their measurement (impact indicators), as a result of the co-design work developed.

SOLUTION	EXPECTED CHANGES	IMPACT INDICATORS	
Healthy habits and low-cost menu workshops in Palmeras	Increased awareness and motivation towards healthy habits	Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits	
	Increased practice of healthy leisure	Practice of healthy leisure	
	Improved social cohesion as a neighbourhood	Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood (not only within one's own patio)	Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood (not only within one's own patio)
		Collective self-esteem	Collective self-esteem
		Social network support	Social network support
	Improved social inclusion	Sense of inclusion	
	Increased time and attention devoted to personal care (NEW, previously considered as context indicator)	Time and attention devoted to personal care	
Improved sense of belonging to the neighbourhood	Sense of belonging to the neighbourhood (not only to one's own patio)		
Sport events and sports for girls in Palmeras	Increased awareness and motivation towards healthy habits (related to sports)	Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits (related to sports)	
	Improved social cohesion as a neighbourhood	Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood	
	Improved social inclusion	Sense of being treated equally as a group	
	Reduced sense of discrimination as a group compared to the rest of the city (NEW, previously considered as context indicator)	Perceived sense of discrimination as a group	
Events and workshops on art, gardening, recycling and culture (including visits outside the neighbourhood)	Improved social cohesion as a neighbourhood	Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood	
		Contact with others in outdoor public spaces	
		Sense of inclusion	
		Freedom to establish personal relationships	
	Improved social engagement	Openness to diversity	
		Social engagement 2 (Persons who are satisfied with their level of involvement in the local community life)	
	Reduced sense of discrimination as a group compared to the rest of the city (NEW, previously considered as context indicator)	Sense of being treated equally as a group	
	Improved equal access to culture and leisure	Perceived sense of discrimination as a group	
	Increased time spent in outdoor public spaces	Equal access to culture and leisure	
	Increased perception of benefits from outdoor public spaces	Time spent in outdoor public spaces	
	Increased quality of free time in public spaces	Benefits from outdoor public spaces	
	Improved sense of belonging and satisfaction with the quality of the neighbourhood	Perceived quality of free time in public spaces	
	Increased culture related well-being and engagement	Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood	
		Participation in cultural activities within outdoor public spaces	
Benefits from culture			
Renovation of public squares and patios in Palmeras	Improved social cohesion as a neighbourhood	Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood	
	Improved social inclusion	Contact with others in outdoor public spaces	
	Improved sense of belonging and satisfaction with the quality of the neighbourhood	Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood	
	Improved quality of free time and leisure in public spaces	Practice of healthy leisure	
		Increased time spent in outdoor public spaces	
		Benefits from outdoor public spaces	
		Perceived quality of free time in outdoor public spaces	
Increased satisfaction with one's surroundings and living environment (economic WBG)	Satisfaction with one's surroundings and living environment		

6. Emerging lessons and recommendations

6.1. Challenges and achievements in the organization and development of the IN-HUB and PPPPs schemes

Public-Private-People Partnerships aim to create more inclusive governance involving different actors, addressing the problems of exclusion and lack of transparency, and including in a more effective way inhabitants' knowledge and participation in the creation of more inclusive environments and services. The IN-HABIT PPPPs approach allowed to include a large spectrum of stakeholders, such as NGOs, civil society, companies, associations, individuals, etc, in the IN-HUB establishment and in the VIS planning and designing processes. The creation of the IN-HUB has been a circular process of participation-engagement process, open to any stakeholder interested.

The first challenge faced by the Cordoba team was to work in a de-structured neighbourhood in a context of pandemics that increased its vulnerability. The disconnection with the city and the stigma of the area made very difficult to build links with and between the inhabitants and between Las Palmeras and the city. The team worked at two levels, creating networks in Las Palmeras and disseminating the project among potential stakeholders in the city to attract their interest to the project and to work in the neighbourhood. The working methods with both groups are different and it has also been necessary to create bridges for the mutual interaction, building spaces where the participants feel comfortable. We are advancing at a good pace, but it is still an issue. The communication channels need to be strengthened and Las Palmeras neighbours empowered to interact on a peer-to-peer basis with other IN-HUB members.

Table 2 gathers the main challenges and the achievements that permitted to overcome them.

Challenges	Achievements
<p>Weak competencies and different abilities to participate in the IN-HUB groups</p>	<p>Participatory problems have been mitigated by the methodologies used in the co-design workshops</p>
<p>Weak participation of the neighbours due to several reasons: basic need to be covered; severe housing conditions; pandemic situation that forced to outdoor meetings (weather conditions influenced open air activities; lack of open spaces; short daylight periods to attend after work hours, care at home, etc.); distrust; lack of experience in collective process; role of woman (care) vs men (not used to be involved/high consumption of cannabis)</p> <p>Difficulty to prioritize the participation in the IN-HUB actions, faced to the needs and urgencies of their precariousness in their daily lives (high vulnerability of the context at the socio-economic level (unemployment, low income, job insecurity, absenteeism and school failure, stigmatization, and socio-geographical isolation.)</p>	<p>Diffusion of the message that participating in IN-HABIT is not a leisure activity but rather a way of thinking "how to live better in my neighbourhood" that benefit and increase health and wellbeing</p> <p>Carry out small concrete and visible actions to promote change</p> <p>Focus on the empowerment of the neighbours (Self-care, motivation and confidence, participation in decision-making and knowledge acquisition, coping skills)</p>
<p>Lack of a tradition of collaboration among the entities working in Las Palmeras: rivalry in hooking the neighbours; lack of long-term financing; negative previous experiences, time needed to build trust (social capital) and to create synergies</p> <p>Understand and mediate the different system of relations and powers existing in the neighbourhood to create and facilitate synergies and participation of different entities and associations.</p> <p>Lack/negative experiences of work towards common goals</p>	<p>Work on reinforcing networking of neighbourhood entities, realizing different actions with common goals to reinforce the co-deployment work</p> <p>Meeting of Las Palmeras entities and neighbourhood representatives every two weeks to organize the Christmas party. This experience triggered as a success story the creation of Las Palmeras Committee, to organize events and activities together and to co-deploy and co-monitor the ITP.</p>
<p>Feeling of administrative abandonment and social exclusion/stigmatization</p> <p>Lack of coordination in the city, with segmented and isolated offers that do not allow to take advantage of the existing capital of the city</p>	<p>High interest and commitment of public and private actors of the city to participate in the IN-HUB and being involved in IN-HABIT</p> <p>Bilateral mediation work with different entities and creation of spaces for interrelation and synergy</p>

<p>Engagement of some groups such as men and youth due to lack of time, interest, and motivation towards change (long-term unemployment, unstructured life, and addictions)</p> <p>The young people potentially more prepared for participation are not interested in the neighbourhood, but on leaving it and do not have much connection with it nor interest in improvements</p>	<p>Proposal of activities in line with the interests of these groups (such as sporting events) and that can enhance their job skills</p> <p>Hire and train people, especially young people, from the neighbourhood to act as role models, enhance the human capital in the neighbourhood beyond the project, and attract other young people</p> <p>Involve the children as a way to engage the rest of the family</p>
<p>Lack of public spaces for neighbourhood meetings</p>	<p>Working to increase security and the feeling of belonging in the neighbourhood, occupying, and improving common spaces with activities and events</p>
<p>COVID limitations: High level of contagion (disinformation, fear, infection/self-isolation)</p>	<p>Door to door, face to face personal meetings, and using associations as an intermediate channel</p>

Table 2: Challenges and achievements.

6.2. Challenges and achievements in combining bottom-up and top-down co-design, mindset change, and social innovations

The combination of bottom-up and top-down methodologies proposed by IN-HABIT has not been a big challenge. The biggest challenge has been the difficulties to work with the different departments in the City Hall. It seems to be disconnection among them, and they tend to work in small groups. In addition, politicians and bureaucrats work is rather detached.

Hence, to link IN-HABIT co-design VIS with the actions of the City Hall is being complicated. Even if the goals are similar, we lack efficient communication channels that could create synergies. Most IN-HABIT actions need coordination of several Departments and often they worked disconnected.

Another difficulty of this phase has been the inclusion of all the target groups in this phase. The most vulnerable groups are also the most excluded from neighbourhood social networks and the most difficult to reach.

6.3. Challenges and achievements in ensuring the GDEI perspective

The GDEI perspective has driven the engagement process, the co-design and co-deployment of VIS and the governance of the IN-HUB. Cordoba IN-HUB aims to investigate challenges and develop innovative solutions to boost equity and inclusion in health and wellbeing, with a particular focus on gender and diversity. In addition, in all its activities, Cordoba IN-HUB aims to promote the fair treatment of any underrepresented group, as well as fair and non-binary language.

Accordingly, the process of stakeholder mapping and engagement was essentially dedicated to reaching out to those people less represented and more at risk of exclusion and discrimination. Disabled, women and in some cases the elderly has been successfully included.

Women are especially vulnerable in Las Palmeras. The core group of IN-HUB residents are predominantly women, as well as their representation in the IN-HUB and in Las Palmeras Committee. IN-HABIT is working to increase their resilience and empowerment and also in education in gender issues, but these are long time process. Education in diversity also needs to be encouraged.

Active older people are also engaged. However, other cases of isolation are more difficult to reach. Actions to attend lonely older people have been proposed.

Many times due to lack of health education and inclusive perspective, cases of physical and mental disability are ignored. This perspective is also applied in all the activities proposed in the VIS.

Cultural difference, in this context, is represented not by immigrants but by ethnic differences between the groups that leave in Las Palmeras. The conflicts, more than racial, are between groups and family clans.

The LGTBIQ+ group is not as representative in the neighbourhood (probably because is not a preferred place to leave), even so its inclusion has been considered in the planning of activities.

6.4. Assessment of and reflection on the Toolkit: methods and tools used in the co-design, co-deployment, and co-management of VIS

The toolkit has been an essential starting tool for the development of the ITP. In any case, due to the highly vulnerable characteristics of the context in Cordoba, a process of profound adaptation of the proposed tools and methodologies has been necessary, as described in previous sections.

The development of this ITP has been challenged by different problems. The main ones are those that have been expressed in the previous section related to participatory processes. Other problems have been:

- Communication: the neighbours have to clearly understand what, why, when and where these actions are carried out.
- Time: cultural changes are very long and complex intergenerational processes in which working on educating in values is fundamental.
- Trust: mistrust towards institutions and negative experiences with previous projects that created false expectations, make essential to continuously demonstrate commitment to concrete actions and a process of caring and cultivating relationships.

6.5. Emerging recommendations: city-specific, comparative among the cities, general

A strong recommendation from the experience of Cordoba city, is that every process in context specific: it is necessary to understand the context (its culture, its social history, the formal and informal functioning of their systems). This step is essential to adapt the objective to the specific needs and to define the intervention community, and at the same time to find the most effective working methodology for the development of the ITP.

To work on an Inclusive Transformation Plan in contexts of high vulnerability is important:

- To disseminate the project between the inhabitants and engage them, offering tangible and real changes that might create positive and concrete impact on their life.
- To encourage neighbours' collaboration and coexistence, building a neighbourhood identity

- To reinforce the sense of security, identity and belonging, through legitimize public spaces as spaces for all the neighbours.
- To reinforce the participation skills, empowering neighbours in health issues, and strengthen networking and organizational skills.
- To assume that these are long-time processes that not always will be successful. However, even if they reach limited results, they always will increase the IHW of some collectives.
- To identify the blocking actors and find strategies to attract them to the plan or if not possible, to minimise their effects.

Appendixes

Appendix 1. Cordoba and Las Palmeras

Appendix 2. Understanding Las Palmeras

The bases of this assessment have been other previous studies carried out by other entities in the neighbourhood, as well as the existing data regarding employment, housing, infrastructure... This has allowed an initial approach, facilitating the identification of the main structural and social factors of the neighbourhood, as well as its potentialities and opportunities for improvement and growth, difficulties, threats...

The neighbourhood of “Las Palmeras” is located at Cordoba outskirts, bounded by one main road, the countryside and a series of buildings that act as a wall, isolating the neighbourhood from the rest of the city. The neighbourhood has an area of approximately 114.000 m², and a total of 2212 people live there. Of the total, 1126 are men and 1086 women, according to the Municipality statistics in 2020. It is worth to mention that existing statistic might poorly reflect the reality, due to the informal economy and the continuous changes in the population leaving there.

The neighbourhood was created in the 60s as the result of a series of floods that affected more than 5.000 people, using this Municipality area to build some portable houses. Later, the area was transferred to the regional authorities, AVRA (Andalucia Housing and Rehabilitation Agency), which built 5 U-shaped buildings with different number of tower blocks between the 1982 and 1992, creating a square in the centre called “Patio”. All blocks have their own patio.

In the first phase, they built 104 households that were offered for rent with option to buy after certain period. The rest (615) were only offered for rent (with low prices) under a “social rent” system.

The houses in general have a poor state of conservation because inhabitants do not feel as owners, and the landowners do not have the means to force them to care. Many families can be housed in the homes of other families or neighbours. There are also sub-human conditions of residence in premises that should not be used as housing and that accommodate entire families, without basic services and with serious unhealthy situations. There are also widespread infrastructure problems, such as sanitation or power outages; high rate of temporary housing and non-payment and evictions.

In terms of naturalization, although the neighbourhood was supposed to host green areas in the different patios, the current infrastructure lacks maintenance or support to be able to replant or modify the soil. However, there are different spaces that might be re-naturalized through

different actions with the neighbourhood, such as planting trees to create shaded spaces in the patios and streets and climbing plants to reuse the existing infrastructure.

Another infrastructure problem is the lack of accessibility in buildings and common spaces. Despite not being high-rise blocks (maximum 4 floors), there is many elderly people and people with children and pushchairs who must go up and down stairs almost daily. This causes many people to reduce their outings to those that are strictly necessary, sometimes completely, thus reducing their social life. This situation reduces their mobility and is harming their mental and physical health, leading to problems of loneliness, physical deterioration...

From the beginning, Las Palmeras emerged as a neighbourhood to place people with low socioeconomic level and facing exclusion problems. During its 50 years of history, the process of structural exclusion has been exacerbated and now affect to the entire population. The geographical situation, the types of housing, the poor state of conservation reveal, the social context and the complicated relations between neighbours are structural problems.

Due to the high rate of temporary housing (most leave the neighbourhood as soon as they can), the disputes between clans and family groups (involving other neighbours), illegal activities... make it difficult to live together and build healthy neighbourhood relationships. The previous factors add to the general feeling of insecurity and fear that many families experience, and reflect the process of de-structuring that the neighbourhood is facing and evidence the lack of a feeling of belonging or identity.

Even though there is a high level of unemployment and very little economic activity according to official data, there is a parallel system of black economy and employment. This submerged economy perpetuates a system of exclusion and illegal activities to continue receiving a minimum income. This situation, together with the high rate of non-payment of rental-fees, other debts that families cannot afford, poor employment opportunities and lack of education and employment, creates a vicious circle difficult to break for many people.

Recently, and as in many other places, the outbreak of covid in the neighbourhood has brought about a series of substantial changes in the environment, reinforcing those negative aspects, becoming a double vulnerability that has brought to light the difficulties and hidden realities that have been unnoticed for long time. As the negative aspects are exacerbated, so are the positive ones. Solidarity, a value with which many of the neighbours identify, has been demonstrated with the support and help of the families, as well as the support of the institutions providing food and medicines.

COVID-19
A doble vulnerability

Figure 33: COVID vulnerability.

Appendix 3. IN-HUB members, partners, and acronyms

1. Entities from Las Palmeras neighbourhood.

Entity (Spanish)	Entity (English)	Acronym	Entity (Spanish)
Asociación Estrella Azahara	Estrella Azahara Association	-	Socio-labour and socio-educational inclusion NGO, with the aim that children, young people and adults who are at risk of social exclusion have a more dignified life
Asociación para la Defensa Social de Adolescentes y Menores	Association for the Social Defence of Youngsters and Minors	ADSAM	ADSAM promotes process of social inclusion of the population that suffers from inequality (social conflict, disability, immigration, ethnic minorities), primarily minors, adolescents, and the elderly
Asociación Red XXI	Red XXI Association	Red XXI	Association that promotes mental health in adolescents; cope with social isolation with alternative sports; job placement and job opportunities (hairdressing, mechanics, etc.); spaces/facilities for adolescents; early childhood cognitive stimulation; provide positive parenting and motherhood skills, promote conflict mediation and non-violent child relationships; prevent additions; gender inclusion; run a comprehensive childhood development centre
CEIP Duque de Rivas	Primary School Duque de Rivas	-	Primary school of Las Palmeras with activities to promote community education
CEIP Pedagogo Garcia Navarro	Primary School Pedagogo Garcia Navarro	-	Primary school of Las Palmeras with activities to promote community education
Escuela de Flamenco	Flamenco School	-	Las Palmeras flamenco school is committed to the conservation of flamenco as an intangible heritage and with other cultural actions. It offers singing, dancing and playing courses
Federación Nacional de Asociaciones de Mujeres gitanas KAMIRA	National Federation of Associations of Roma Women KAMIRA	KAMIRA	Federation of Roma women's associations focused on education, families, housing, employment, discrimination, gender violence and health services
Hermanidad de la Piedad	Piedad Brotherhood	-	Religious group based in the neighbourhood church with a commitment to social development

Parroquia Santa María de Claret	Santa María de Claret Church	-	Church of the neighbourhood with social programs for neighbours. It offers its premises to work in them to any actors interested in the socio-economic development of the neighbourhood
Onda Palmeras Radio	Onda Palmeras Radio Station	-	Community radio broadcasting the neighbourhood news, with open participation programs

2. Entities from the Cordoba.

Entity (Spanish)	Entity (English)	Acronym	
Agencia de Vivienda y Rehabilitación de Andalucía	Housing and Rehabilitation Agency of Andalucía	AVRA	The Andalusian Housing and Rehabilitation Agency is a public company of the Andalucía government, attached to the Regional Ministry of Development, Infrastructure and Territory Planning that owns the buildings of Las Palmeras
Amasce SCA	Amasce SCA	AMASCE	Architecture, design and art cooperative that creates spaces and processes centred on people, culture and communities in cities
Asociación Axerquía Verde	Green Axerquia Association	-	Association aiming to the renaturalization and the planting of micro forests in the historical city centre as a strategy to fight climate change
Asociación de Allegados y Personas con Enfermedad Mental de Córdoba	Association of Relatives and People with Mental Illness of Córdoba	ASAENEC	Association of Friends and People with Mental Illness of Córdoba is a non-profit organization made up of relatives, friends and people with mental illness, united in the search for new solutions that contribute to improve the quality and life expectancy of people with mental illness and their families, and to defend and promote their rights and freedoms
Bosque Anxanar	Bosque Anxanar	-	Company working in social development through eco-sustainable participatory workshops and activities
Club UNESCO Cordoba	UNESCO Club Cordoba	CUCO	UNESCO Club aiming to develop the UN 2030 Agenda Project and the SDGs (People, Planet, Alliance, Peace and Prosperity) through the culture
Confederación de Empresarios de Córdoba	Confederation of Entrepreneurs of Córdoba	CECO	Union of companies and entrepreneurs, with resources and professionals for the promotion of companies and the creation of entrepreneurial networks

Corduba Tech	Corduba Tech	-	Association of companies and entities of the technological sector of Córdoba
Ecologistas en Acción Córdoba	Ecologists in Action Cordoba	-	Association for the defence of nature, the environment and flora and fauna. It promotes the natural heritage and defends its conservation.
Federación Andaluza de Empresas Cooperativas de Trabajo	Andalusian Federation of Cooperative Working Companies	FAECTA	Andalusian Federation of Work Cooperative Companies that promotes the creation of work cooperatives, working also in marginalised neighbourhood
Festival Flora	Flora Festival	FLORA	Artistic Festival that launch every year a competition among top floral artists in the world to create floral modern art installations in institutional patios of Córdoba.
Fundación ARTDECOR	ARTDECOR Foundation	-	Foundation leading the project Cordoba City of Ideas, a creative pole that work as a meeting point platform for cultural projects in the city and to boost cultural enterprises.
Fundación DON BOSCO	Don Bosco Foundation	-	Foundation that develops projects of residential care, socio-educational, socio-labour insertion, support for formal education, fight against the digital divide, community promotion, as well as social volunteering initiatives
Fundación La Caixa	La Caixa Foundation	-	Social Foundation of the CAIXA Bank which, in collaboration with different entities, works together to fight poverty and exclusion, promote health research, make culture available to all and improve children's education
Grayhats	Grayhats	-	ICT company expert in cloud computing, data analytics and digital security
Hospital San Juan de Dios de Córdoba	San Juan de Dios Hospital	-	The Hospital Order supports a comprehensive care model focused on the assisted person and their social and family environment, adapted to the challenges of today's society, with the aim of promoting and improving people's health and their quality of life without distinction for gender issue
IES Galileo Galilei	Secondary School Galileo Galilei	-	Institute of Secondary Education with practice in social integration, promotion in equality and gardening and landscape

Instituto Andaluz de la Mujer	Andalusian Institute for Women	IAM	Institute dependent on the Ministry of Equality, Social Policies and Conciliation for the promotion of gender equality
Instituto Municipal de Gestión Medio Ambiental - Real Jardín Botánico de Córdoba	Municipal Environmental Management Institute - Royal Botanical Garden	INGEMA	Cordoba Botanical Garden. Together with the multiple plant exhibitions, it offers extensive experience in the renaturalisation of ponds, providing the materials, resources, means... to implement them. They also work with healthy eating, natural dyes, conservation and care of plants, plant decoration, vertical gardens...
Mercacórdoba S.A.	Mercacordoba S.A.	-	Municipal supply market for companies and entities. It offers several lines of work in relation to entrepreneurship and food. They offer material resources and raw materials
Museo de Bellas Artes de Córdoba	Fine Arts Museum of Cordoba	-	Cordoba Art Museum, with experience in teaching art and heritage in an active and dynamic way, committed to the dissemination and promotion of art and culture
Patios Axerquía	Axerquia Patios	PAX	Association dedicated to promoting social innovation processes for urban regeneration in areas of high heritage value in the city centre of Cordoba
Robokids	Robokids	-	Company dedicated to the training and intellectual development of the youngest, using ICT as the cornerstone of their activities
Saneamientos de Córdoba	Sanitation of Cordoba	SADECO	Municipal waste management company, fully involved in recycling, circular economy and educational trainings and workshops
Universidad de Sevilla	Sevilla University	US	The University of Seville collaborates through the TAR research group, focused on engineering to transform urban environments

Appendix 4. Secondary data from Cordoba

- City profile:

Statistics administrative registration Cordoba City Council (01/01/2019):
<https://www.cordoba.es/la-ciudad/cifras-estadisticas/estadisticas-de-poblacion>

o Cordoba city:

Total inhabitants: 328.718 (Men: 157.888; Women: 170.830)

Level of education by sex	Men	Women	Total
Not Applicable (less than 16 years old)	31919	29693	61612
Analphabetic (not writing nor reading)	3	5	8
Analphabetic (not writing nor reading)	591	2276	2867
Title inferior to primary school grade	1	4	5
No studies. Writing and reading	12199	17339	29538
Incomplete primary school. Five grades EGB	22144	25859	48003
Obligatory school graduate or equivalent	20	28	48
Elementary bachelor. School graduate. EGB Completed.	36663	32784	69447
Professional Formation First Degree	7293	9322	16615
Bachelor, Professional Formation Second Degree	8	17	25
Professional Formation Second Degree	6847	7453	14300
Superior Bachelor. BUP or LOGSE.	12820	12045	24865
Other medium education titles (clinical assistant, secretary...)	1035	1000	2035
Diploma of university school (Business...)	6154	13058	19212
Diploma of university school (Architect or technical engineer)	2727	696	3423
University degree. Architect or superior engineer.	13365	14879	28244
Superior Studies Title (non-university)	196	77	273
PhD or postgraduate studies	3890	4289	8179
Not known	13	6	19
Total population	157888	170830	328718

Table 3: Level of education by sex (Cordoba city).

o Las Palmeras Neighbourhood:

<u>Immigrant population by country of origin</u>	
Brazil	1
Bulgaria	1
Ecuador	1
France	1
Maroc	11
Romania	1
Total (without Spain)	16
Total	16

<u>Population by Nationality</u>	
Brazil	1
Bulgaria	1
Ecuador	1
France	1
Maroc	11
Romania	1
Total (without Spain)	16
Spain	2276
Total	2292

Table 4: Immigrants and nationalities in Las Palmeras.

<u>Level of education by sex</u>	Men	Women	Total
Not Applicable (less than 16 years old)	367	358	
Analphabetic (not writing nor reading)	29	86	
No studies. Writing and reading	356	296	
Incomplete primary school. Five grades EGB	197	170	
Obligatory school graduate or equivalent	201	174	
Professional Formation First Degree	13	16	
Bachelor, Professional Formation Second Degree	3	2	
Superior Bachelor. BUP or LOGSE.	2	4	
Diploma of university school (Business...)	7	4	
Diploma of university school (Architect or technical engineer)	2	3	
University degree. Architect or superior engineer.	1	0	
Superior Studies Title (non-university)	1	0	
Total population	1179	1113	

Table 5: Level of education by sex in Las Palmeras neighbourhood.

Appendix 5. Initial Stakeholder mapping

Graph 1: Stakeholder mapping Córdoba.

Appendix 6. Manifest of Adhesion to the IN-HUB Cordoba

Manifiesto of adhesion to IN-HUB Córdoba of the IN-HABIT Project

IN-HABIT: INclusiveHealth And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

IN-HABIT is an **ambitious research project** funded by Horizon 2020 and coordinated by the University of Córdoba that will be developed over 5 years (2020 -2025) in four cities in Europe: **Córdoba (Spain), Riga (Latvia), Lucca (Italy) and Nitra (Slovakia)**.

Small and medium-sized cities play a **key role** in the transition to a sustainable society and in preventing and mitigating socio-economic and environmental inequalities in accessto health and well-being, and it is important to have research tailored to their needs.

The 4 cities aim to **investigate the effects of combining and integrating different innovations** (inspired by nature, cultural, social, technological and digital) in improving people's **health and well-being**, through an **inclusive, gender, equity and diversity approach**.

The role that undervalued resources such as **culture and heritage (Cordoba), food (Riga), links with animals (Lucca), and art and the environment (Nitra)** can play in these improvements will be analyzed.

IN-HABIT actions will be implemented in selected **public spaces** in each of the 4 cities and will preferably focus on **disadvantaged areas** and **vulnerable groups** whose access to health and well-being is more limited.

The innovations to be implemented in each city will be **co-designed , co-executed and co-managed** with local stakeholders and will seek to drive behavioural and mindset changes that promote inclusive health and well-being . To this end, the IN-HUB Córdoba (IN: inclusive, HUB: nucleus of interaction) is created, a laboratory of action and social innovation. This IN-HUB will be made up of people, collectives, organizations and institutions of the city that will be involved in the actions of the project , contributing knowledge and ideas and creating synergies with other actions underway.

This manifesto wants to be a commitment to participation in the IN-HUB Córdoba and will be a living document in which the roles, levels of commitment, the form of management and the internal regulations of the IN-HUB will be established through a participatory process.

The IN-HUB Córdoba will be made up of working groups that will meet at least once a quarter to co-design different innovative solutions and co-manage their progress and implementation . The IN-HUB Córdoba will meet at least once a year to share the progress made in the work tables and in the project.

DOCUMENT OF ADHESION

Name and Surname NIF

On your behalf or

Representing the organization

through the position of

States that:

- The person/entity that they represent is familiar with the Manifesto of Adherence to the IN-HUB Córdoba of the H2020 IN-HABIT Project and shares its principles and objectives.

- The person/entity wishes to contribute to the fulfillment of the commitments established by the IN-HUB Córdoba from its field of action, and to participate in the development of innovative actions or initiatives that are launched.

- Express the agreement to be recognized from now on as a person/entity attached to the IN-HABIT Project, showing the agreement to receive information derived from its development by the following means:

Expresses its interest in participating in the following areas of work:

- Wellbeing and health
- Culture, heritage and art
- Gender, diversity, inclusion and social innovation
- Naturalization and Environment
- Infrastructure, technology and digitization

And with the following level of involvement:

- Continuous (participation in the lines of work and in the co-design, co-implementation and co-management of actions, search for synergies with other actions, etc.)
- Punctual (participate in specific activities, advise on actions in which I have experience, etc.)
- Information channel (knowledge of actions, exchange of information/activities, etc.)

In _____, on _____, 2021/2022

Signature:

Este proyecto ha recibido financiación del programa de investigación e innovación Horizonte 2020 de la Unión Europea en virtud del acuerdo de subvención nº 869227

Appendix 7. Cordoba IHW indicators

Sub-dimension	Expected change (P=partners' view / C=citizens' view)	Indicator	Description
Social cohesion	Improved social relations (C)	Satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood	Persons who declare a good/very good level of satisfaction with personal relationships in the neighbourhood/living area (Quantitative/Self-reported/Key Impact Indicator)
	Increased trust among people (P)	Trust in others	persons who declare a good/very good level of trust in other persons within their community (Qualitative/Self-Reported/Key Impact Indicator)
	Improved social network support (P)	Social network support	Persons who rely on getting help from services organized by associations, neighbourhood committees, groups of citizens (including visiting services) (Quantitative and qualitative/Self-reported /Key Impact Indicator)
Perception of security	Increased sense of safety (C)	Sense of safety at night	Persons who feel safe walking at night in the city (Quantitative/Self-reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		Sense of safety in green areas	Persons who feel safe to walk in the public green areas of their neighbourhood (Quantitative/Self-reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		Perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area	Average level of crime, violence and vandalism in the neighbourhood perceived by persons on a range from 1-10 (Quantitative/Self-reported/Key Impact Indicator)
Social Inclusion	Increased social relations in public spaces (P; C)	Contact with others in public spaces	Persons who get together with friends and relatives in public spaces once a week (Quantitative/Self-reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		Domestic Isolation	Persons who spend the majority of their time alone at home (Qualitative/self-reported/Key impact indicator)
	Improved sense of inclusion (P;C)	Sense of inclusion	Persons who feel to be part of the community (Quantitative and qualitative/Self-reported/Key Impact Indicator)
	Improved civil engagement and democratic participation (C)	Civil engagement 1	Persons who declare to take part to democratic life at city level (neighbourhood committees, municipal or school councils, election committees, political parties) (Quantitative/Self-reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		Civil engagement 2	Persons who believe they can influence local policies/political decisions (Qualitative/Self-Reported/Key Impact Indicator)
	Improved social engagement (P; C)	Social engagement 1	Persons who declare to participate in voluntary activities (social, cultural, educational, religious) (Quantitative/Self-reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		Social engagement 2	Persons who are satisfied with their level of involvement in the local community life Qualitative/Self-Reported/Key Impact Indicator
		Social engagement 3	People who are committed to take care of public spaces and green areas in their neighbourhood (Qualitative/Self-Reported/Key Impact Indicator)

	Improved openness to diversity (C)	Openness to diversity	Persons who are open towards new values and alternative way of living and thinking (Qualitative/self-reported/key impact indicator)
	Increased change-making attitude (P; C)	Change-making attitude	Persons who believe they can change the reality of their neighbourhood (social situation, beauty/attractiveness of the space, economic situation)
Equality	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Sense of being treated equally	Persons who feel they are treated with less courtesy and respect than others (or other groups) (Qualitative/Self-reported/Context indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Access to internet from home	Persons who have access to internet from home (Quantitative/Self-reported/Context Indicator)
	Improved equal access to culture and leisure (P)	Equal access to culture and leisure	Persons who believe to have the same opportunity than others to access the available cultural and leisure opportunities in their city/neighbourhood (Qualitative/Self-Reported/Key Impact Indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Obstacles for the access to Culture and leisure	Persons who think to have economic, time, family, mobility, cognitive, cultural obstacles in the access to culture and leisure opportunities in their city/neighbourhood (Quantitative and qualitative/Self-reported /context Indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Obstacles for the access to social care services and health services	Persons who think to have economic, time, family, mobility, cognitive, linguistic/cultural, social obstacles in the access to social care and health services in their city/neighbourhood (qualitative/Self-reported /context Indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Obstacles for the access to training opportunities	Persons who think to have economic, time, family, mobility, cognitive, linguistic/cultural, social obstacles in the access to training opportunities in their city (Qualitative and quantitative/Self-reported /context Indicator)
Discrimination	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Perception of discrimination in society	Persons who believe that minority groups are considered dangerous/dishonest/ criminals/ unreliable/ bad neighbours by local citizens (qualitative/Self-reported /context Indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Perceived personal condition of discrimination	Persons who can describe themselves as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in their country. (qualitative/Self-reported /context Indicator)
	increased collective self-esteem (C)	Collective self-esteem	Persons who feel proud of their community, feel a sense of self-esteem as a community (Qualitative self-reported/key impact indicator)

Spatial wellbeing	Improved accessibility of local resources (P)	Accessibility of local resources	Persons who think in their neighbourhood is easy to find help from others; find job opportunities; training opportunities; find safe, pleasant and accessible green areas, participate in cultural events; find adequate social and health assistance, find a place to do sports, find healthy food, find children playgrounds, moving on foot, moving by bike (Qualitative and Quantitative /Self-reported /Key Impact Indicator)
	Improved satisfaction with urban green areas (P; C)	Satisfaction with urban green areas	Persons who are satisfied with public green areas of their neighbourhood in terms of accessibility, safety, inclusiveness, beauty, comfort (Quantitative/Self-reported / Key impact indicator)
	Increased inclusiveness of public squares and green areas (P)	Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas	Persons who feel free to access, to use and to move within the public squares and green areas in their neighbourhood (Quantitative and qualitative/Self-reported /Key Impact Indicator)
	Improved air quality perception (P)	Air pollution perception	Persons who think that the quality of air in their neighbourhood is satisfactory/good (Quantitative/Self-reported / Key impact indicator)
	Improved sense of belonging and satisfaction with the quality of the neighbourhood (P; C)	Sense of belonging and perception of the neighbourhood	Number of persons who like their neighbourhood; who think that it has a good reputation; who think that the image of the neighbourhood has improved in the past two years; who think it could attract more tourists in the next years; who would not move to another neighbourhood (Qualitative and Quantitative /Self-reported /Key Impact Indicator)

Table 6: IHW Indicators to measure social wellbeing in Cordoba.

Sub-dimension	Expected change (P=partners' view / C=citizens' view)	Indicator	Description
Physical health status	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Self-reported health status	Average level of physical health reported by persons on a 5 points scales (Quantitative/Self-reported / context indicator)
Determinants of health	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Practice of physical activity	Frequency of practice of physical activity in a week (Quantitative /Self-reported / context indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Time spent on food preparation at home	Average time spent by persons preparing their meals at home in a day (Quantitative/Self-reported / context indicator)
	Increased consumption of self-grown fruit and vegetables	Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption	Persons who declare to consume self-grown fruit and vegetables (Qualitative/Self-reported /Key Impact Indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Consumption of fruits and vegetables	Persons who declare to consume fresh fruits and vegetables on a daily basis (Quantitative/Self-reported / context indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Access to healthy and nutritious food	Persons who were unable to eat healthy and nutritious food in the last week (Quantitative/Self-reported / context indicator)
	Increased awareness and motivation towards healthy habits (C)	Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits	Persons who are aware about healthy habits and motivated to change their lifestyles (Qualitative/self-reported/ Key Impact Indicator)
Sports practice	Increased practice of sports in public green areas (P; C)	Practice of sports in public green areas	Frequency of use of the public outdoor/green areas to do sports in a week (Quantitative and qualitative/Self-reported / Key impact indicator)
	Increased perception of benefits from sports (P)	Benefits from sports	Persons who think that sports/physical activity contributes to their wellbeing (qualitative/Self-reported /Key impact indicator)
Cultural consumption and production	Increased satisfaction with cultural facilities (P)	Satisfaction with cultural facilities	Persons who are satisfied with the cultural places/events and opportunities in their neighbourhood (Quantitative/Self-reported / Key impact indicator)
	Increased participation in cultural activities within public spaces (P)	Participation in cultural activities within public spaces (outdoor/indoor)	Frequency of participation in cultural activities/consumptions in public squares, green areas, centres of their neighbourhood in a week (Quantitative/Self-reported / Key impact indicator)
	Increased perception of benefits from culture (P)	Benefits from culture	Persons who think that cultural activity contributes to their wellbeing (qualitative/Self-reported /Key impact indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Cultural consumptions	Average time devoted to cultural consumptions during the week (theatre, reading books, cinema, exhibitions) (Quantitative/self-reported/context indicator)
	Increased local cultural engagement (P)	Local cultural engagement	Persons directly involved in the organization, production and management of cultural activities, products, places and events in their neighbourhood (Quantitative self-reported/ key impact indicator)
Leisure/Free time	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Time devoted to leisure and personal care	Average time (hours) devoted to leisure and personal care in a typical working day (Quantitative/Self-reported / context indicator)

Increased practice of healthy leisure (C)	Practice of healthy leisure	People who practice healthy behaviours for leisure /avoid unhealthy leisure (Qualitative /Self-reported /Key Impact Indicator)
Increased time spent playing relaxing or doing sports in public green areas (P)	Time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas	Average time (hours) spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas in a day (Quantitative/Self-reported / Key impact indicator)
Increased time spent in social and recreational public spaces (P)	Time spent in social and recreational public spaces	Average time spent in social and recreational public spaces in a day (Quantitative/Self-reported / Key impact indicator)
No change expected - context indicator (P)	Time devoted to family care	Average time in a day devoted to family care (Quantitative/Self-reported / context indicator)
No change expected - context indicator (P)	Time devoted to pets' care/playing with pets	Average time devoted to pets' care/playing with pets in a day (Quantitative/Self-reported / context indicator)
No change expected - context indicator (P)	Satisfaction with free time use	Persons who are satisfied with the quality of their free time/the way they spend their free time (Quantitative/Self-reported / context indicator)
Increased perception of benefits from social and recreational public spaces (P)	Benefits from social and recreational public spaces	Persons who think that social and recreational public spaces contribute to their wellbeing (Qualitative self-reported/key impact indicator)

Table 7: IHW Indicators to measure healthy lifestyles in Cordoba.

Sub-dimension	Expected change (P=partners' view / C=citizens' view)	Indicator	Description
Employability	Increased employability of people (P)	Opportunity to find a job in the city	Persons who are satisfied with the opportunities offered by the job market at city level (Qualitative/self-reported/key impact indicator)
		Expected sector of occupation	Persons who think they can find a job in NBS related sector in the next 6 months (Qualitative/self-reported/key impact indicator)
	Increased satisfaction with one's skills and competences (P)	Satisfaction with one's own competencies, skills 1	Persons who are satisfied with their level of skills and competences (Qualitative/self-reported/key impact indicator)
		Satisfaction with one's own competencies, skills 2	Persons who think that their education, skills, and competences will be helpful to find a paid job in the city (Qualitative/self-reported/key impact indicator)
Financial situation	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Feeling that one's basic needs are met	Persons who believe that their basic needs are sufficiently met (Quantitative/Self-reported /context indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Satisfaction with time and resources for personal care	Number of persons who think to have sufficient resources to manage personal matters/personal care
	Increased satisfaction with one's surroundings and living environment (P; C)	Satisfaction with one's surroundings/living environment	Satisfaction related to one's own surroundings/living environment (qualitative/Self-reported /Key impact indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Satisfactions with one's own financial situation	Average level of satisfaction related to one's own family or individual income and resources (Quantitative/Self-reported /context indicator)

Table 8: IHW Indicators to measure economic wellbeing in Cordoba.

Appendix 8. VIS proposed in the ITP

Health and Wellbeing

HARD VIS

1A.1 Sport facilities in the neighbourhood	
Description	Create spaces to practice different types of sport. Specific attention will be devoted to spaces for women and girls sport practices and public facilities for intergenerational sports
Stakeholders involved	Sport Clubs, CEIP Duque de Rivas, CEIP Pedagogo García Navarro
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles/Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Sports practice
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating in sport activities. Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption. Number of sports facilities installed in the neighbourhood. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles

1A.2 Public areas as safe playground spaces	
Description	Creation in the public areas of Las Palmeras of playground areas to create safe and pleasant areas to different inhabitants. Las Palmeras has no children nor elder play facilities
Stakeholders involved	CalleJugando
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles/Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Leisure and free time
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of playground areas. Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles

SOFT VIS

1B.1 Healthy habits workshops	
Description	Workshops with neighbours to promote healthy diets, healthy habits related to food consumption, how to cook fresh food, sugar-free diets... Training in the importance of sport and healthy habits to keep a healthy lifestyle
Stakeholders involved	MERCACORDOBA, Chefs, CUCO, Sport Clubs
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles/Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Physical health status; Determinants of health
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of workshops carried out. Number of topics covered. Number of food education initiatives. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles.

1B.2 Local sport activities and events	
Description	Promotion, support and participation in events that promote healthy habits, such as La Milla (The Mile), a popular race organised in Las Palmeras with participants from all the city, to promote healthy habits and links with the city and to break the stigma or CalleJugando (Playing in the Streets) events celebrated in different parts of the city using traditional games made with recycled materials, to vindicate the use of public spaces as safe areas for people and to promote healthy open-air leisure).
Stakeholders involved	Las Palmeras Football Club, Calle Jugando, CEIP Pedagogo García Navarro, CEIP Duque de Rivas
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Sports practice; Leisure and free time
Monitoring	Number of sport activities carried out. Number of inclusive activities developed. Number of persons by PCs participating in sport activities. Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles

1B.3 Sport activities for women and girls	
Description	Organization of sport and dancing activities. Creation of clubs or groups of participants to promote the role of women and girls in sports.
Stakeholders involved	Las Palmeras Football Club, Sport Clubs, NGOs
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing / Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Equality / Sport practice
Monitoring	Number of sport activities carried out. Number of inclusive activities developed. Number of persons by PCs participating in sport activities. Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption. Activities for the promotion of new roles for women. Perceived increase in social wellbeing Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles

1B.4 Self-care and inclusive wellbeing activities	
Description	Activities focused on personal wellbeing and self-care (meditation, yoga, self-knowledge, natural cosmetics)
Stakeholders involved	Bosque Anxanar, ASAENEC
IHW Dimensions	Mental health / Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Positive emotions / Physical health status
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of activities carried out. Number of topics covered. Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles. Perceived increase in psychological wellbeing/mental health.

1B.5 Healthy low-cost menus	
Description	Healthy food workshops to train families on the preparation of daily menus made with low-cost products or products from food banks
Stakeholders involved	MERCACORDOBA, Chefs, NGOs
IHW Dimensions	Economic wellbeing / Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Financial situation / Physical health status
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of workshops carried out. Number of Food education initiatives. Number of citizens by PCs engaged in healthier lifestyles and food consumption. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles. Perceived increase in economic wellbeing.

1B.6 Business incubation activities	
Description	Actions to promote entrepreneurship and the implementation of training activities focused on employment. Actions to increase job opportunities and coaching and mentoring for entities that work in this field. Realization of a program of assessment, support, follow-up... of the enterprise for six months through a competition for innovative entrepreneurial ideas.
Stakeholders involved	B4B, FAECTA
IHW Dimensions	Economic wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Employment; Job and skills satisfaction
Monitoring	Number of entrepreneurs by PCs participating in business incubation activities. Number of activities carried out. Number of persons by PCs employed in jobs linked to IN-HABIT. Perceived increase in economic wellbeing.

1B.7 Periodic radio program	
Description	An IN-HABIT periodic radio program (once a month for the moment) is running from January 2021 in Las Palmeras Radio Station. Inhabitants, stakeholders, and researchers participate to disseminate news of the project and encourage people to take an active role in the transformation of the neighbourhood. The program is also used to boost empowerment, improve participation and communication skills and promote participation in the project activities
Stakeholders involved	Red XXI, Onda Palmeras
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing / Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Social cohesion; Social inclusion / Leisure and free time
Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of programmes broadcasted. Social impact of the programs Perceived increase in communication skills Perceived increase in social wellbeing Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles

Culture, Heritage and Art

HARD VIS

2A.1 Artistic creations in patios	
Description	Creation of meaningful murals and paintings in the neighbourhood to make it a more pleasant environment and to reinforce a positive identity (i.e., a mural of the life of teenagers who have finished the secondary school). Artists will be invited to work with locals to support them in the acquisition of artistic competences
Stakeholders involved	SADECO, Bosque Anxanar, CUCO, ARTDECOR, Arts schools
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles/Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Cultural participation
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of actions carried out. Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups. Number of spaces for art production & exhibition. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles Perceived increase in social wellbeing
2A.2 Mobile and fix exhibition furniture	
Description	Panels will be designed and built in the patios in order to create a space for non-permanent exhibitions to attract culture and art to Las Palmeras. Furniture will be built with recycled and sustainable materials and with the collaboration of inhabitants
Stakeholders involved	ARTDECOR
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Spatial wellbeing
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of actions carried out. Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups. Number of spaces for art production & exhibition. Perceived increase in social wellbeing.

SOFT VIS

2B.1 Cultural events	
Description	Artistic creations and performances in the neighbourhood, run by neighbours (e.g., Celebration of cultural week, Culture and Sustainability Conferences, artistic performances, festivals....)
Stakeholders involved	CUCO, CEIP Pedagogo García Navarro, CEIP Duque de Rivas, RED XXI, Estrella Azahara, ARTDECOR
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Cultural participation
Monitoring	Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups. Number of spaces for art production & exhibition. Creative festivals and fair. Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of persons by PCs involved. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles

2B.2 Culture, heritage and arts workshops	
Description	Activities run in natural environments and cultural sites will be offered to Las Palmeras and other city inhabitants to engage them in joint activities and promote wellbeing
Stakeholders involved	CUCO, Red XXI, Museum of Fine Arts, INGEMA
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles/Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Cultural participation; Determinants of health
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of activities carried out. Number of topics covered. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles Perceived increase in social wellbeing

2B.3 Healthy, sustainable and cultural walks	
Description	Monthly walks to visit artistic and cultural events in the city will be organised to help Las Palmeras inhabitants to rediscover Cordoba's culture and heritage. These shared experiences aim to reinforce the belonging to the city and the feeling of community; to cultivate the values of respect for the natural and build environment and to appreciating the importance of caring for it
Stakeholders involved	CUCO, INGEMA, Museum of Fine Arts, FLORA
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles/Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Cultural participation; Leisure and free time
Monitoring	Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups. Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of persons by PCs involved. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles Perceived increase in social wellbeing

2B.4 Cultural 'recipes' to improve health and wellbeing	
Description	"Health prescriptions" based on the substitution of medicines by cultural or nature activities, that may help to improve mental health and wellbeing (nature walks, cultural visits, crafts...)
Stakeholders involved	San Juan de Dios Hospital, Cruz Roja Volunteers
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles / Mental health
IHW subdimension	Cultural participation; Physical health status / Psychological wellbeing
Monitoring	Number of collaborating entities. Number of prescriptions issued. Number of participants. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles. Perceived increase in psychological wellbeing/mental health.

2B.5 Virtual Museum of Las Palmeras	
Description	Creation of an interactive virtual museum with the social history and the memories of the neighbourhood (visual material, biographies, documents, popular knowledge and ethnic-cultural traditions)
Stakeholders involved	Red XXI, Estrella Azahara, CEIP Pedagogo García Navarro, CEIP Duque de Rivas, Hermandad, Parroquia, Escuela de Flamenco, Neighbours
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Social cohesion; Social inclusion
Monitoring	Virtual museum created. Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of actions carried out. Number of topics covered. Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups. Perceived increase in social wellbeing

2B.6 Activities for the promotion and dissemination of intangible cultural heritage and natural heritage	
Description	Workshops and activities based on the intangible heritage and culture of the city of Córdoba, which allow its dissemination and knowledge by the population as backbone elements of culture and as an identifying feature of identity and character
Stakeholders involved	CUCO, Red XXI, INGEMA, Museum of Fine Arts
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles/Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Determinants of health; Cultural participation
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of actions carried out. Number of topics covered. Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles Perceived increase in social wellbein

2B.7 Flamenco dressing parade	
Description	Organization of a workshop to design and sewing flamenco costumes. Celebration of a parade and fashion show in the city centre to display the results and attract potential clients
Stakeholders involved	Flamenco schools, Dressing cooperatives
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing/Economic wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Cultural participation; Leisure and free time
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating in the workshop. Number of persons by PCs attending to the parade by PCs involved in the organisation. Number of new clients attracted Number of costumes sold Perceived increase in social wellbeing Perceived increase in economic wellbeing

2B.8 Joint cultural activities between artists from the neighbourhood and the city	
Description	Activities both in the neighbourhood and in the rest of the city that allow the creation of cultural meeting points between artists, to show the social and human capital existing in the neighbourhood. Links with projects running in the city, such as Cordoba Ciudad de las Ideas that attract artists to the city, will support these actions
Stakeholders involved	ARTDECOR, Museum of Fine Arts
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing / Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Social cohesion; Social inclusion / Cultural participation
Monitoring	Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups. Number of spaces for art production & exhibition. Number of creative festivals and fair. Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of persons by PCs involved. Perceived increase in social wellbeing. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles.

Gender, Diversity, Inclusion, and Social Innovation

SOFT VIS

3B.1 Las Palmeras Committee	
Description	Start-up of Las Palmeras Committee made up of the different entities that take their action to improve the neighbourhood and its conditions, promoting the active participation of the different social actors for community change. It intends to meet every two weeks to co-deploy this ITP, share the different lines of action and actions of each entity, adding synergies and establishing joint actions to energize the neighbours.
Stakeholders involved	Red XXI, Estrella Azahara, CEIP Pedagogo García Navaro, CEIP Duque de Rivas, Hermandad, Parroquia, Escuela de Flamenco, Neighbours
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Social inclusion
Monitoring	Number of meetings held. Number of joint actions co-deployed. Number of inclusive activities developed. Number of initiatives integrating different social groups. Number of persons by PCs participating. Perceived increase in social wellbeing

3B.2 Mindset change activities to promote empowerment and inclusion	
Description	Workshops with FIDS (Feel- Imagine- Do- Share) methodology that help builds social and emotional competencies and promotes employability skills. Workshops and training for inhabitant's empowerment through I CAN activities and promoting community participation with inclusive perspective
Stakeholders involved	DFC, ASAENEC, Estrella Azahara, Red XXI, IES Galileo Galilei
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Discrimination; Social inclusion; Equality
Monitoring	Number of workshops developed Number of persons by PCs involved in mindset change activities. Number of educators by PCs trained in mindset change. Number of inclusive activities developed. Perceived increase in social wellbeing

3B.3 Mapping of the talents and abilities of the neighbours	
Description	Mapping of neighbourhood talents to activate human capital, empower people, generating positive self-perception and employment/training opportunities, and deconstructing stigmas. A door-to-door interview has been developed to know the skills of each inhabitant. The map will be used to promote jobs and time banks.
Stakeholders involved	Estrella Azahara, Red XXI
IHW Dimensions	Mental health / Healthy lifestyles / Economic wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Positive emotions / Determinants of health; Cultural participation / Employment
Monitoring	Map of talents. Number of joint actions with the neighbours. Number of inclusive activities developed. Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups. Number of persons by PCs participating. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles. Perceived increase in psychological wellbeing/mental health.

3B.4 Creation of women safe spaces	
Description	Creation of a "Purple Point" conceived as a protected listening space where women can express themselves and find relief. Organization of activities to work on socio-emotional skills and competencies to empower women in the face of gender violence and discrimination
Stakeholders involved	ASAENEC, Federación KAMIRA, IES Galileo Galilei
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Equality / Discrimination
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of sessions hosted Activities for the promotion of new roles for women. Number of inclusive activities developed. Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups. Perceived increase in social wellbeing

3B.5 Behavioural games	
Description	Through technology, resort to the use of incentives and reward, behavioural games to increase health and wellbeing and raise awareness about certain aspects of social relevance such as gender violence will be developed
Stakeholders involved	UREAD, TSR
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Determinants of health
Monitoring	Number of participants by PCs. Number of editions of the games developed Behavioural games fostered by the games Perceived increase in social wellbeing.

3B.6 Prevention of violence workshops	
Description	Workshops to promote values of coexistence and respect with a gender perspective at different levels: gender, intrafamilial, against children
Stakeholders involved	ASAENEC, Federación KAMIRA, Red XXI
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing / Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Equality; Social inclusion; Crime/security and violence / Physical health status
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of workshops carried out. Number of topics covered. Activities for the promotion of new roles for women. Number of inclusive activities developed. Perceived increase in social wellbeing Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles

Naturalization and Environment

HARD VIS

4A.1 Naturalization of patios (squares)	
Description	Naturalization of patios, where the neighbours can enjoy the benefits of vegetation and socialize in the common areas, through the installation of green areas, mobile and adaptable flower beds, pergolas, shaded areas... Native plants and trees adapted to the climatic conditions will be planted. Recycled structures and materials will be used, adapted to each patio and co-designed and made by neighbours
Stakeholders involved	IES Galileo Galilei, INGEMA, SADECO, Bosque Anxanar
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Spatial wellbeing
Monitoring	Number of patios renaturalised. Mobile furniture created. M2 of new accessible green space created. M2 of community gardens. M2 of new shaded areas. Perceived increase in social wellbeing

1A.2 Natural ponds	
Description	Building of natural ponds without chlorine and regulated by biodiversity, creating a full ecosystem that could be used for investigation and educational purposes. The ponds would be maintained and cared by trained neighbours and volunteers from city NGOs.
Stakeholders involved	INGEMA, Fundación La Caixa, CUCO
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Spatial wellbeing
Monitoring	M2 of new accessible green space created. Number of new ponds. Number of different species living in ponds (biodiversity). Perceived increase in social wellbeing

4A.3 Urban orchards	
Description	Start-up and reactivation of urban orchards so that neighbours can grow their own food, creating an ecological system of sustenance for families with fewer resources. They would allow their use for therapeutic and educational purposes, responding not only to food but also obtaining resources such as composting, dyes, decorative elements... Its co-deployment would allow the promotion of community structures, collaboration between neighbours, entities...
Stakeholders involved	INGEMA, IES Galileo Galilei
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Physical health status; Leisure and free time
Monitoring	M2 of organic food growing initiatives. M2 of community gardens. Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of different species cultivated. Number of food education initiatives. Number of families involved in healthier food habits. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles

4A.4 Implement a (permanent) FLORA artistic creation in the neighbourhood	
Description	Design and creation of a floral creation for the FLORA Festival in the neighbourhood. FLORA is an annual International Festival of Floral Modern Art in Cordoba's patios created by international artists. These temporary creations are located in the most emblematic patios and never in vulnerable areas. It will be built by the residents with living plants, but the installation is intended to be permanent and accessible to people, as a living creation, becoming a point of reference for the neighbourhood and also attracting visitors and tourists. Its care and maintenance would be carried out by neighbours.
Stakeholders involved	FLORA, IES Galileo Galilei
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles/Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Cultural participation
Monitoring	Artistic floral creation. Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of visitor by PCs. Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles Perceived increase in social wellbeing.

4A.5 Therapeutical and inclusive garden	
Description	Creation of an inclusive garden based on taste, touch, and smell to promote sensory stimulation for people with sensory difficulties in one of the patios.
Stakeholders involved	FLORA, INGEMA, IES Galileo Galilei, People with different abilities, NGOs
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Social inclusion; Equality
Monitoring	M2 of new accessible green space created. M2 of therapy gardens. Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of visitors by PCs. Perceived increase in social wellbeing

SOFT VIS

4B.1 Intangible corridor with Axerquia inhabitants	
Description	Creation of a network of interactions between neighbours of Las Palmeras and Axerquía to share traditional knowledge on the ecological and social management of patios, its maintenance, social structures... The objective is to share the positive aspects of each model to strengthen the creation of communities among the people who live in each courtyard, replicating the social and ecological structure of the Axerquía patios in Palmeras. But also to create links and interactions between the inhabitants of both quarters and break the traditional isolation of Las Palmeras and its ghetto stigma. Different joint activities will be proposed
Stakeholders involved	PAX, AXERQUIA Association
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Social inclusion; Social cohesion; Spatial wellbeing
Monitoring	Number of crossed visits/activities organised. Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups. Number of persons by PCs participating. Perceived increase in social wellbeing
4B.2 Training and workshops in natural and gardening care	
Description	Training in the field of gardening and caring for plants, so that residents are able to be the main caretakers of their neighbourhood and the plants that will be planted, as well as for work and employment purposes.
Stakeholders involved	Bosque Anxanar, INGEMA, ADSAM
IHW Dimensions	Economic wellbeing / Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Employment / Leisure and free time
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of trainings carried out. Number of jobs created. Perceived increase in economic wellbeing. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles

4B.3 Training and workshops in floral creations	
Description	Training based on the planning of floral compositions and flower care, which include the planning of compositions, their development and construction, care... based on workshops that allow the acquisition of job skills. At the same time, the creations will serve to embellish the neighbourhoods and the participant dwellings. Several trainings will be organised every year and people from Cordoba invited to work with people from Las Palmeras. Some trainings will be conducted by FLORA artists
Stakeholders involved	IES Galileo Galilei, FLORA, INGEMA
IHW Dimensions	Economic wellbeing / Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Employment / Leisure and free time
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of trainings carried out. Number of floral creations made. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles. Perceived increase in economic wellbeing.
4B.4 Training and workshops for recycling and reuse materials	
Description	Workshops on recycling and reuse of materials to reduce waste and have a positive impact on the environment, creating more sustainable homes and cleaner spaces. They aim to be subsequently used for the construction of recycled infrastructures and furniture that will embellish the patios, thus creating more environmentally friendly neighbourhood. Inhabitants will acquire job and entrepreneurship skills
Stakeholders involved	SADECO, INGEMA, IES Galileo Galilei
IHW Dimensions	Economic wellbeing / Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Financial situation / Leisure and free time
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of trainings carried out. Number of topics covered. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles. Perceived increase in economic wellbeing.
4B.5 Therapy gardening activities	
Description	Activities based on gardening as a tool for sensory stimulation, relaxation, stress elimination, motor stimulation in the elderly and people with motor difficulties, etc. These activities will also use gardening as an element of cohesion and elimination of barriers, promoting the empowerment of the most excluded people and allowing the development of new motor and social skills.
Stakeholders involved	ASAENEC, ADSAM
IHW Dimensions	Mental health / Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Psychological wellbeing / Social inclusion
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of activities carried out. Number of topics covered. Perceived increase in psychological wellbeing/mental health. Perceived increase in social wellbeing.

4B.6 Celebration of “Los Patios Festival” in the neighbourhood	
Description	Celebration of the Festival de los Patios in Las Palmeras. This Festival is run in May in the patios of the historical city and attract an amazing number of visitors. The proposal is to include Las Palmeras patios (once naturalised and decorated) in the tour and to try to attract visitors to the area. IN-HABIT aims to design patios that include all the traditional aspects that make them up, but also incorporate the social aspects of the context and the characteristics of the environment. Its implementation would be based on the concept of the patio of the future as a pilot test, incorporating a more sustainable and ecological vision, through edible plants, with low water consumption, native species which allow better temperature control, etc.
Stakeholders involved	PAX, INGEMA, AXERQUIA Association,
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing / Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Spatial wellbeing / Determinants of health
Monitoring	Inclusion of Las Palmeras patios in the institutional tour. Number of visitors Number of inclusive activities developed. M2 of sustainable and inclusive patios. Number of cultural initiatives integrating different social groups. Number of persons by PCs participating. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles. Perceived increase in social wellbeing.

Infrastructure, Technology, and Digitalization

HARD VIS

5A.1 Sustainable lighting infrastructures in patios	
Description	Deployment of sustainable lighting system adapted to the context of the neighbourhood, which allows the lighting of the darkest areas in an innovative way to increase the safety of the environment and the people.
Stakeholders involved	AVRA, LABORELEC
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Crime/security and violence: Spatial wellbeing
Monitoring	Number of lights installed. Number of zones in which the lighting improves. Assessment of the increase in the perception of security. Perceived increase in social wellbeing

5A.2 Inclusive, friendly and ecological urban furniture in patios	
Description	Design and installation of inclusive furniture (some of them made by neighbours), adapted to the needs of the neighbourhood, made in a sustainable way. It would be based on the concept of friendly architecture, allowing multiple uses and responding to questions of comfort, cleanliness, use of public space... Collaboration with partner SUA in Nitra will be boosted
Stakeholders involved	AMASCE SCA, SUA
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing/Economic wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Spatial wellbeing
Monitoring	Number of people by PCs involved in making the furniture Number of jobs created Quantity of furniture installed. Variety of urban furniture installed. Increased accessibility of urban furniture. Perceived increase in social wellbeing. Perceived increase in economic wellbeing.

5A.3 Hotspots of wi-fi access in patios	
Description	Installation of Wi-Fi points in the patios to allow free access to the internet responding to a need for many neighbours.
Stakeholders involved	LABORELEC, Corduba Tech
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Leisure and free time / Equality
Monitoring	Number of access points installed. Wi-Fi network coverage. Number of neighbours benefited. Perceived increase in social wellbeing.

5A.4 Platform and sensors for environmental monitoring of patios	
Description	Implementation of a platform for monitoring the environmental variables of the patios that allows their study and the implementation of specific actions to improve the quality of life.
Stakeholders involved	WTG, PAX
IHW Dimensions	Economic wellbeing / Healthy lifestyles
IHW subdimension	Housing / Determinants of health
Monitoring	Digital citizen engagement platform to connect users and data. Number of persons by PCs participating. Monitoring points equipped with sensors. Number of variables reflected. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles. Perceived increase in economic wellbeing.

5A.5 Structural and support elements for patios using 3D printing, recycled materials...	
Description	Deployment of sustainable structures and facilities for the different activities in the patios, through the use of recycled, 3D printed, reused materials...linked to trainings to promote employment in these fields
Stakeholders involved	SADECO, AMASCE SCA, Fundación Don Bosco
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles / Economic wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Cultural participation / Employment
Monitoring	Number of structures implemented. Number of structures designed. Number of people by PCs involved. Number of people that improve their job skills. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles. Perceived increase in economic wellbeing.

SOFT VIS

5B.1 Training in digital and technological skills	
Description	Workshops in which digital skills are worked on in a transversal and didactic way, such as 3D design and printing, audio-visuals and e-administration. These workshops could be delivered by youngsters in risk of exclusion from other parts of the city that are being trained on them. The peer-to-peer interaction can facilitate the buy-in of the activities by Las Palmeras youngsters
Stakeholders involved	Fundación Don Bosco, Robokids
IHW Dimensions	Social wellbeing / Economic wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Equality / Employment; Job and skills satisfaction
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of trainings carried out. Number of topics covered. Number of people that improve their job skills. Perceived increase in social wellbeing. Perceived increase in economic wellbeing.

5B.2 Vocational training on specific jobs	
Description	Specific (ad-hoc) workshops and training adapted to the needs and expectations of local inhabitants and the development of the above-mentioned activities will be organised to allow the neighbours acquire useful training and skills to get a job.
Stakeholders involved	Federacion KAMIRA, Estrella Azahara, IES Galileo Galilei, Robokids, Red XXI, Mercacórdoba
IHW Dimensions	Economic wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Employment; Job and skills satisfaction
Monitoring	Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of trainings carried out. Number of topics covered. Number of people that improve their job skills. Number of persons by PCs employed in jobs thanks to IN-HABIT. Number of inclusive activities developed. Perceived increase in economic wellbeing.

5B.3 DAO as governance model for patios	
Description	Design and deployment of a Decentralized Autonomous Organization (DAO) as a mechanism for governance and co-management of patios as an innovative and ground-breaking element. DAOs are organizations run through smart contracts deployed over blockchain systems with no central leadership where decision-taking is bottom-up; ideas, rules and protocols take on a life of their own and are able to incentivize people to make them happen; and funds are self-managed. Additionally, a digital token will be created not as a currency, but as an immutable and non-transferable reputational token that confers reputation to people, neighbours, or stakeholders, in particular domains or skills.
Stakeholders involved	GrayHats, Corduba Tech
IHW Dimensions	Healthy lifestyles/Social wellbeing
IHW subdimension	Determinants of health
Monitoring	Implementation of a DAO. Number of persons by PCs participating. Number of activities carried out. Perceived increase in healthier lifestyles. Perceived increase in social wellbeing.